

D2.1. Patient-centric cases and requirements definition

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable 2.1 Description

Deliverable 2.1 reports in detail the medical requirements and patient-centric use cases for the project. It is the outcome of the work conducted within Task 2.1 “Patient-centric cases and requirements definition”. According to the Grant Agreement, the objective of Task 2.1 is to identify possible use cases and describe high level technical and functional criteria that would be required by the ThrombUS+ innovative wearable system to detect, screen, monitor and thus prevent DVT. This is only the first step of the co-design process set under Work Package 2 (WP2), which is to continue in the following Tasks 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 with the integration of specific regulatory, technical and functional requirements, thus ensuring a feasible design which appropriately addresses the clinical needs while remaining acceptable to the users. The present work is based on the collection and processing of medical information for several patients’ profiles provided by the clinical experts of the consortium (ATHENA, CSS-IRCSS, GNP, HSV, LSMU and TAU) and by specific clinicians that participated in additional targeted consultations.

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMI	Body Mass Index
DoA	Description of Action
DVT	Deep vein thrombosis
EC	European Commission
EEA	Ethics External Advisor
EU	European Union
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HCD	Human-centred design
HTA	Health technology assessment
ICT	Information and communication technology
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LMWH	Low molecular weight heparin
MAFEIP	Monitoring and Assessment Framework for the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing
NCD	Noncommunicable Diseases
PE	Pulmonary embolism
PPH	Post-partum haemorrhage
QALY	Quality of Life Years of Patients
RUC(s)	Reference use case(s)
TL	Task Leader
VTE	Venous thromboembolism
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1. Executive Summary

The overall objective of WP2 is to contribute to the device's co-design process by integrating medical needs, technical and regulatory requirements, as well as user acceptability constraints in a set of possible scenarios based on deep vein thrombosis related patient conditions. As the first step of WP2, this deliverable (D2.1) aims to identify patient-centred use cases for the ThrombUS+ device and describe initial high level functional criteria that should be considered in the co-design process for each of such use cases.

The present work is based on the collection and processing of medical information for several patients' profiles provided by the clinical experts of the ThrombUS+ consortium (members of the ATHENA, CSS-IRCSS, GNP, HSV, LSMU and TAU research teams), validated through a rapid review of relevant academic literature, and deepened and expanded upon interviews with medical experts that participated in additional targeted consultations. The collection and processing of the evidence collected led to the creation of seven Reference Use Cases (RUCs), intended to encompass respective sets of prevalent DVT patient profiles with similar main baseline clinical conditions or treatment. The seven RUCs identified are: (1) **Neurosurgery**, (2) **Lower limb orthopaedic surgery**, (3) **Cardiovascular surgery and risk**, (4) **Pregnancy and postpartum**, (5) **Obesity**, (6) **Cancer and oncological treatment**, (7) **Autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders**.

For each of the RUCs, a description of the general clinical circumstances of the case and in particular the needs of the respective patients in relation to the screening and monitoring of possible DVT is presented. The high-level requirements for the usability and acceptability of the device are also addressed, thus accounting for the basic functional requirements necessary for each case. Having RUCs as a measure of analysis and comparison consequently allows consideration of both the added value of the potential ThrombUS+ device for each patient's journey and the (possibly) divergent technical and functional requirements to ensure the innovation's usability, acceptability and cost-effectiveness in relation to each RUC.

In conclusion, the use case analysis revealed the following

- In terms of usability, the potential for the ThrombUS+ device to improve early detection of DVT and thus reduce its fatal consequences in an efficient way would already be a significant step forward, given the relatively low level of confidence of current methods and the high incidence of asymptomatic cases.
- In terms of acceptability, all cases stressed the importance of ensuring a fresh, comfortable, and non-invasive wearable design, as well as a simple and effective interaction between the components and users.
- In terms of cost-effectiveness, it was logically highlighted that as long as the wearable device reduces clinical staff workload and the use of high-cost equipment, while increasing detection capacity, the impact would be expected to be positive. Remarkably, the use cases identified highlight a window of opportunity to create a device that could be used outside of the clinical setting, supported by the fact that approximately 3 out of 4 DVT or PE events occur outside the hospital.

Finally, the technical means that the tool may use must be carefully weighed against medical contraindications and the limits set by the complexity of use and acceptability of the design. It is therefore relevant to discern at the next stages whether the device is to be designed with the aim of covering certain cases within the identified possible scenarios (and therefore adapted to their specific usability and acceptability needs) or whether a universally applicable design can be technically aimed for (a scenario that is likely to depend on technical possibilities).

Based on the outcomes of D2.1 and the work conducted within Task 2.1, the co-creation process to establish the needs and requirements will continue in the following tasks with the integration of specific regulatory, technical and functional requirements. ThrombUS+ will thus ensure a feasible design of the wearable device which appropriately addresses the clinical needs while remaining acceptable to the users.

2. Introduction

2.1. Purpose of the Deliverable

Despite its remarkable prevalence and the high severity of its associated potentially fatal complications (i.e. pulmonary embolism (PE)), the detection of deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is nowadays still largely unreliable. This is due, on the one hand, to the fact that a large proportion of DVT cases are asymptomatic even up to the point where pulmonary embolism has already developed. On the other hand, there is a lack of accurate DVT prediction and detection mechanisms, even in hospitalized or high-risk patients, which results in DVT-caused pulmonary embolism to be regarded as “the most common preventable cause of hospital death”¹. Such a situation creates the need for developing effective methods to increase early detection rates and reduce preventable deaths at the point of care.

In this context, the ThrombUS+ project aims to develop a wearable device that combines ultrasound imaging, plethysmography techniques and light reflection rheography with artificial intelligence (AI) technology for point-of-care continuous monitoring and early detection of DVT signals. This device is especially intended for patients who remain at significant risk of DVT despite preventive measures or prophylaxis, such as those undergoing long surgeries, that are immobile or even pregnant. Identifying the main functional characteristics and needs of these patients is fundamental to the optimization of the design of the device and to the success of this innovation.

The objective of this deliverable (D2.1) is **to identify possible significant use cases for the ThrombUS+ device and to describe the initial functional criteria that should be considered in the co-design process for each of the use cases**. From the preliminary intended purpose of the envisioned device (see Figure 1) and mindful of the very early stage of the technological development, the exercise conducted and hereby presented aims to contribute to the device’s co-design process by **integrating medical needs, technical and regulatory requirements and user acceptability constraints in a set of possible scenarios based on DVT-related patient conditions**. In this way, it seeks to generate knowledge of the functional circumstances in which the ThrombUS+ device could add the most value from a **patient-centred approach**, ensuring that it is both useful for clinical purposes and acceptable to both patients and medical professionals.

ThrombUS+ is an active wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, continuous monitoring in patients with high deep vein thrombosis (DVT) risk, that is applied to the patient's lower limb. For this purpose, ThrombUS+ uses ultrasound, electrical impedance plethysmography, and light reflection rheography.

Additionally, ThrombUS+ is used for DVT prophylaxis by monitoring the patient's lower limb activity during mobilization and guiding the patient according to physiotherapeutic exercise plans. For this purpose, ThrombUS+ uses activity sensors.

ThrombUS+ is intended for application to adult patients in the clinical environment by healthcare professionals.

Figure 1. Preliminary intended purpose of the ThrombUS+ device as drafted in the D2.2-Regulatory framework, security, safety and ethics strategy and guidelines².

¹ Maynard G. Preventing hospital-associated venous thromboembolism: a guide for effective quality improvement, 2nd ed. Rockville, MD: Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality; October 2015. AHRQ Publication No. 16-0001-EF.

² Prinz T. et al., in preparation

These scenarios, hereafter referred to as **Reference Use Cases (RUCs)**, are intended to encompass respective sets of prevalent DVT patient profiles with similar main baseline clinical conditions or treatment. Having RUCs as a measure of analysis and comparison consequently allows consideration of both the added value of the potential ThrombUS+ device for each patient’s journey and the (possibly) divergent technical and functional requirements to ensure the innovation's **usability, acceptability and cost-effectiveness** in relation to each RUC.

2.2. Context and structure of the Deliverable

Deliverable 2.1 is the outcome of the work conducted within Task 2.1 “Patient-centric cases and requirements definition” and constitutes only the first step of the co-design process set under WP2: “Requirements and product co-design”, which aims to identify the required functional specifications for the ThrombUS+ device and define its overall design drawing from patient-centric use cases, and the corresponding technical and regulatory requirements – including security, safety, ethical and privacy requirements. Following the present deliverable and building upon the use cases hereby described the work under WP2 is to continue in the following months with the integration of specific regulatory, technical and functional requirements, thus allowing to co-develop a feasible and safe design which appropriately addresses the clinical needs while remaining acceptable by the users (Figure 2).

The work done within the Task 2.1 in particular will inform the technology developments envisaged under WP3, WP4 and WP5, as it establishes certain key functional margins for device usability and acceptability to which the technology will have to fit. Tasks 2.2 and 2.3 will then establish requirements that subsequent work must satisfy. To ensure the integration of the developed hardware and software components with the established requirements, a series of tasks are foreseen in WP6. Furthermore, the clinical studies foreseen in the context of WP7, and particularly its evaluation phase, will allow further elaboration of the challenges identified at this early stage.

Figure 2. Gantt chart of the WP2 detailing the individual tasks and their durations. Due months of WP2 deliverables (D2.1, D2.2, D2.3 and D2.4) as well as projects Milestones are indicated (M2, M3, M4).

In the following sections the human-centred methodology applied for the construction of the RUCs and the data collection processes performed are presented (Methodology). Then, the identified RUCs are described

together with a set of linked user *Personas* (Results: Reference Use Cases and *Personas*). For each of the RUCs, a description of the general clinical circumstances of the case and in particular the needs of the respective patients in relation to the screening and monitoring of possible DVT is presented. The high-level requirements for the usability and acceptability of the device are also addressed, thus accounting for the basic functional requirements necessary for each case.

The present deliverable is produced in the beginning of the ThrombUS+ project and is based on a draft purpose and on an early and limited understanding of the technology under development. It is therefore based on preliminary expectations and not on available technology, which means that all identified criteria and assessments regarding design, usability, acceptability or cost-effectiveness issues are preliminary and are intended precisely to allow the consortium to make decisions based on a more complete understanding of the needs of patients and clinicians with respect to the potential device in the next steps. This deliverable is not intended in itself to establish exclusion or inclusion criteria for the choice of use cases for the device, but to inform in a more refined way the factors to be taken into account for such a decision, which may be necessary at a more advanced stage of the project. The clinical trials foreseen in the context of the project will provide key information to refine the design of the product according to the functional requirements of the use cases that are considered most relevant.

3. Methodology

Making the ThrombUS+ wearable device both useful for clinical purposes and acceptable to the end users (patients and clinicians) is key to the success and impact of the project. To these aims, it is critical to consider the needs, values and experiences of the patients, as well as those of the potential operators (not only clinicians, but other caregivers, family members, etc.) from the very beginning of the initial co-design process. In this sense, the methodology proposed and conducted as explained below aims to integrate these factors on the basis of a practical, experience-centred understanding of the design approach. The following subsections present the five “steps” adopted (and to be adopted) in this process of identifying the RUCs and the functional criteria to ensure a design that meets the intended usability and acceptability goals of the ThrombUS+ device (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The 5 methodology steps for implementing and completing WP2. This deliverable implements steps 0 to 3.

In order to provide a personalized and patient experience-focused solution, human-centred design was adopted from the outset as the guiding design framework (Step 0 – Human-centred design and patient-centred care). From this perspective, a process of information gathering focused on the practical experience of the project's clinical partners was devised to identify the most relevant DVT-related patient profiles, based on a series of conditions preliminary regarded as relevant. This was complemented by a rapid literature review of DVT concurrent conditions increasing risk (Step 1 – Patient profiling).

Based on the information collected in the previous steps, seven RUCs were constructed on generic clinical conditions. To refine and deepen these, interviews with medical specialists of the respective conditions were conducted to learn more about the risks, possibilities and functional needs related to them. The information collected by these means was systematized and fed into the present deliverable and the construction of the user *Personas* (Step 3 – Reference use cases and creation of *Personas*).

The last step, which exceeds this deliverable, will be the integration of what is here submitted with the results of Tasks 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 at the end of WP2, resulting in a set of key specifications for the co-design of the device in the subsequent stages of the project (Step 4 – Next steps: Integration with regulatory and technical requirements for co-design).

3.1. Step 0 – Human-centred design and patient-centred care

Human-centred design (HCD) is a systemic approach to intervention designing that builds on the experiences, capabilities, needs and desires of the very people who interact with what is designed. Focused on human needs and how design can address those needs, HCD drives designers to properly understand people, early engage stakeholders and envision outcomes at the organizational and collective levels. In HCD, design “denotes the act of intentionally creating something meaningful”³.

In the healthcare realm, this approach leverages the integration of patients’ needs and individual care experiences into the problem and context understanding, as well as into the solution-developing processes, thereby combining patient-centred care and intervention HCD^{4,5}. Such an approach relies on the traditions of ethnography, participatory design, co-design, contextual design, among others, and allows to 1) uncover the essential needs of essential stakeholders involved in the success of the medical technology, 2) generate creative solutions, 3) quickly and effectively evaluate product alternatives, and 4) provide solutions that satisfy the critical needs of direct users and other stakeholders⁶.

Accordingly, HCD product development models are organized in several subsequent phases, that relate to each other by means of iteration (Figure 4):

1. Understanding the context of use (the right people and the right problem).
2. Specifying user requirements in enough detail to drive design.
3. Designing solutions that meet the requirements.
4. Evaluating solutions against the requirements.
5. Adapting the final design to meet the user requirements.

Along with the key role of the **contextualized definition of the problem** to be solved, two more characteristics of the HCD process stand out: first, the **early and continuous participation of the stakeholders** affected by the design in the development process. Second, the **iterations**, which allow the solution to be built, tested, re-built and re-tested, incorporating the feedback out of the testing in an agile way. In the context of the ThrombUS+ co-design and development process, adopting these steps and strategies will allow improved outcomes.

The work under WP2 entails building a thorough understanding of the context of use, to then find the intersections with what is technically feasible and economically and regulatorily viable, thereby covering

³ Fisher, M. J., & Johansen, E. (2020). Human-centered design for medical devices and diagnostics in global health. *Global Health Innovation*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.15641/ghi.v3i1.762>

⁴ Melles, M., Albayrak, A., & Goossens, R. (2020). Innovating health care: Key characteristics of human-centered design. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 33(Suppl 1), 37-44. <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzaa127>

⁵ Mullaney, T., Pettersson, H., Nyholm, T., & Stolterman, E. 2012 Dec 22. Thinking beyond the Cure: A Case for Human-Centered Design in Cancer Care. *International Journal of Design* [Online] 6:3. Available: <https://www.ijdesign.org/index.php/IJDesign/article/view/1076>

⁶ Fisher, M. J., & Johansen, E. (2020). Human-centered design for medical devices and diagnostics in global health. *Global Health Innovation*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.15641/ghi.v3i1.762>

phases 1 and 2, and fostering a smooth unfolding of phase 3. Under Task 2.1 stakeholders⁷ have been actively involved in helping to understand and specify the possible contexts of use and the main functional desires and needs of potential users (patients and clinicians) that the solution must take into account in order to solve the problem it is intended to address (phase 1). Such operational scenarios are to be refined through the specification of requirements according to regulatory and technical constraints, which are the focus of Tasks 2.2 and 2.3 (phase 2). This integrated work will finally lead to the generation of the first wearable strap design with an integrated human perspective under Task 2.4 (first step of phase 3).

Figure 4. The human-centred design process as outlined in the ISO standard 9241-210:2019 (en) Ergonomics of human-system interaction - Part 210: Human-centred design for interactive systems⁸.

The subsequent phases (3 to 5) and its iterations will be covered by the activities conducted under WP3 to WP7 of the project. These will likely involve several iterations of designing, testing, re-designing and re-testing prototypes. Expectedly, during the ThrombUS+ wearable device development process, at least three full-circle iterations will take place following the initial conceptual design, the prototype design (ranging from low-fidelity prototyping to high-fidelity prototyping), and the final product design.

In short, stakeholder integration and successive iterations will complement the context and problem understanding provided by this deliverable (which will be further refined through the clinical trials), ensuring that users' socio-technical factors are included in the product decision-making. Thus, taking the HCD

⁷ Notably, the term 'stakeholder' implies that not only the direct end-users of a system will be involved in the co-design process, but anyone affected by the introduction of the system. For ThrombUS+, stakeholders may include patients, informal caregivers, healthcare professionals, industry partners, etcetera. Ideally, stakeholders are involved in each HCD phase, even though the role can be different, ranging from acting as a traditional research subject (e.g., participating in an interview to analyse the end-users wants and needs, evaluating user requirements, or testing a prototype) to being a member of the design team (as ThrombUS+ project partners do by participating in co-design sessions and being part of the decision-making process).

⁸ A possibility is to combine in the co-design process both ISO 9241-210:2019 and IEC 62366-1 standards, since the latter regards medical devices and may also be relevant in the context of ThrombUS+. However, due to its highly technical nature and the fact that it aims at mitigating risks associated with correct use and use errors, it may be appropriate to assess once the technical features and specific design of the device are further developed.

approach will enable us to make sure that during the whole process of co-design and development of the ThrombUS+ device medical needs, technical possibilities, regulatory requirements, and the socio-technical particularities of the potential users are optimally combined.

3.2. Step 1 – Patient profiling and Reference Use Cases

3.2.1. Patient profiling rationale

The potential patient population with DVT-related conditions is enormous. According to a recent study the incidence of venous thromboembolism (VTE) —which comprises DVT and PE— in Europe and the United States is estimated at about 1 to 2 per 1000 person-years, resulting in hundreds of thousands or even millions of cases per year in these regions⁹. The scientific literature concurs in pointing out that the risk of DVT is multifactorial and that the risk triggers are also numerous and of disparate impact, according to different demographic, behavioural, genetic or acquired clinical characteristics of the patients. Consequently, there are a myriad of possible combinations of factors that may or may not be found in a patient with potential DVT, meaning that the use cases for a device such as ThrombUS+ may also be quite broad and varied.

However, although in a high percentage (24-40%) of incidents of DVT or PE the triggering factor is unclear, unknown or unreported¹⁰, there are certain clinical conditions, treatments and other concurrent basal or acquired factors that are known to increase the likelihood of a person developing DVT and consequently being exposed to the associated risks, such as PE, recurrent thrombosis or post-thrombotic syndrome. To cite just a few disparate risk triggering factors examples the literature deems relevant, all orthopaedical surgery, hospitalization, pregnancy, oral contraceptives or older age, account for an increased risk of potential DVT¹¹. Each of these clinical conditions, treatments and concurrent features generate different needs for both patients and healthcare professionals.

Despite this complex scenario and with a view to deepen the understanding of the problem and its context to then identify the most relevant use cases, a strategy was put in place to collect the practical experiences of the ThrombUS+ clinical partners in relation to actual DVT screening and treating processes. For this purpose, an online questionnaire was created based on a preliminary list of clinical and other basal relevant conditions (Table 1), which were grouped in the questionnaire under the concept of "patient profiles" (Figure 5).

The patient profiling aims to identify in a personalised and human-centred way the potential users of ThrombUS+, considering the possible overlap of medical conditions or risk factors for DVT, as well as the functional characteristics, interests and needs that individuals may have in relation to the use of the product. Key to this is identifying those conditions that are either more prevalent, or risky, or would benefit the most from continuous monitoring.

Figure 5. Patient profiling definition as provided for in Step 1 questionnaire.

The design of the questionnaire was discussed and refined with ThrombUS+ WP2 partners and the project coordinators in several internal virtual meetings. The shared goal was to generate a set of questions that

⁹ Lutsey, P. L., & Zakai, N. A. (2023). Epidemiology and prevention of venous thromboembolism. *Nature Reviews Cardiology*, 20(4), 248-262. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41569-022-00787-6>

¹⁰ Heit, J. A., Spencer, F. A., & White, R. H. (2016). The epidemiology of venous thromboembolism. *Journal of Thrombosis and Thrombolysis*, 41(1), 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11239-015-1311-6>

¹¹ Lutsey, P. L., & Zakai, N. A. (2023). Epidemiology and prevention of venous thromboembolism. *Nature Reviews Cardiology*, 20(4), 248-262. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41569-022-00787-6>

would be at the same time useful for the construction of the use cases, easy to answer, and that would allow for scientifically robust responses. This resulted in a set of questions, per patient profile, on the prevalence of the related baseline condition increasing DVT likelihood, the incidence of DVT among patients with such baseline condition, and the corresponding risk ratio. Finally, a qualitative (subjective) assessment was requested on the basis of a low/medium/high scale of the potential added value of a continuous DVT monitoring device (see Annex 1 – Step 1 Patient profiling table).

The preliminary categories and subcategories of patient profiles on which this questionnaire was based are listed in Table 1 below. ThrombUS+ clinical partners were asked to respond to the questionnaires by focusing on the profiles that most closely matched their expertise and daily practice and to provide supporting scientific sources whenever possible.

Table 1. Preliminary patient profiles (as adapted from Step 1 questionnaire).

#	Patient profile	Subcategory
1	After surgery or trauma	Hip, legs or pelvis Other orthopaedic Neurosurgery Cardiac/Thoracic/Vascular Other (please specify)
2	Pregnant woman or recent birth	
3	History of blood clotting disorders	Family history of blood clotting disorders Personal history of DVT or pulmonary embolism Other (please specify)
4	Cancer	Chemotherapy Central venous catheter
5	Other medical conditions increasing blood clotting risk	Cardiac Pulmonary Autoimmune diseases (APS, Lupus vasculitis, IBD) Oral contraceptives HRT Varicose veins Other (please specify)
6	Smoker or history of smoking	
7	Obese or overweight	
8	Genetic disorders	Factor V Leiden Prothrombin gene mutation Other (please specify)
9	Inactive or immobile for long periods of time (not post-surgery)	
10	Other (please specify)	

3.2.2. Clinical partners' input processing and Reference Use Cases building

Step 1 questionnaires were answered by various departments of all clinical partners inside the ThrombUS+ consortium, as shown in Table 2 below. In total, around 80 patient profiles were identified, and 91

bibliographical references were provided (see Annex 2 - Step 1 Literature References). The responses and references received separately from each partner were consolidated in a single Microsoft Excel document to facilitate the subsequent processing and analysis.

Expectedly, responses to the questionnaires varied in terms of accuracy, specificity and completeness. Where necessary, missing information was complemented with a rapid literature review, thereby using the latest scientific insights to complement any significant gaps (Cross-cutting and overlapping factors through literature review). However, in all, the large number and variety of the profiles provided allowed to gather a lot of valuable information and helped to identify the most significant use cases from the perspective of the consortium partners.

Table 2. Respondent Clinical Departments for defining patient’s profiles (Step 1).

Clinical partner	Respondent Area/Department
ATHENA	Anatomy Pathology Internal Medicine Clinical Epidemiology
CSS-IRCCS	Thrombosis and Haemostasis Unit/Obstetrics and Gynaecology
GNP	Academic Orthopaedic Cardiology
HSV	Radiology Orthopaedic Surgery Emergency Room
LSMU	Neurosurgery Orthopaedics & Traumatology Vascular Surgery
TAU	n/d

The approximately 80 patient profiles collected under Step 1 were processed and assessed against the findings of the rapid literature review on concurrent conditions (see below Cross-cutting and overlapping factors through literature review). Some important findings promptly emerged from the processing of the information provided. First, many of the patient profiles identified were found to be highly specific (for example, severe traumatic brain injury with neurological deficit), suggesting that the universe of use cases would perhaps become too narrow for this early stage of product design. Second, there were cases with likely overlaps in terms of both the clinical approach and the added value that a device such as the ThrombUS+ could bring (for instance, hip, knees or pelvis surgery). Third, we noted that the preliminary patient profiling options used in the questionnaire did not necessarily best reflect the universe of patients with the highest prevalence or risk of DVT, nor were they the best possible categories for benchmarking the functional criteria that a device such as ThrombUS+ would require.

Thus, taking into account both the information on prevalence and incidence of DVT and the potential overlap in terms of patient-user needs, we undertook a clustering exercise of the cases provided by the questionnaire. In this decision we sought to balance the need to have a meaningful number of reference cases that was at the same time relatively generic so as to cover a relevant group of patients at high risk of developing DVT, yet specific enough to allow us to identify the different functional requirements of a potential device applicable to each case. In this context, we reasoned that it was adequate that the selection

and regrouping of profiles was primarily driven by the similarity of patient profiles with respect to the nature of the baseline clinical condition (which functions as the main, but not the only, trigger for potential DVT).

The clinical proximity between clustered profiles also implies commonalities between the types and processes of treatment and the medical professionals involved, thus reinforcing the possibility of identifying common functional criteria. It is also important to note that the identification of reference categories was also driven by the prevalence of baseline conditions and their impact on DVT risk, as it was noted that certain profiles of more generalised conditions (such as obesity or pregnancy) could in themselves imply the existence of a sufficiently relevant patient universe that would justify specific functional criteria. The clustering exercise explained above resulted in the construction of a set of seven reference scenarios, which we named Reference Use Cases (RUCs). The seven RUCs and the corresponding patient profiles encompassed in each of them can be found in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Patient Profiles per encompassing Reference Use Case (based on Step 1 questionnaire responses)

Having RUCs as a measure of analysis allows to investigate and compare both the added value of the potential ThrombUS+ device for each RUC patient’s journey and the divergent functional requirements to ensure the innovation’s **usability**, **acceptability** and **cost-effectiveness**. The operationalization of these last three concepts, closely linked to the context of use, is a key to the identification of the basic functional criteria of co-design from a patient-centred perspective.

- The **usability** is defined as “the extent to which a system, product or service can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use”¹² and in ThrombUS+ case relates to the possibility of increasing the sensitivity, specificity, speed and/or confidence of screening procedures and early detection of DVT, thereby improving prophylaxis decisions and reducing the risk of fatal consequences. The usability is highly dependent on the technical possibilities the technological innovation may provide and its integration into DVT screening and monitoring protocols in clinical settings.

¹² As defined by the ISO in ISO 9241-11:2018(en) Ergonomics of human-system interaction — Part 11: Usability: Definitions and concepts, <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:9241:-11:ed-2:v1:en>, last accessed: 15 June 2024. It is also relevant to take into account in this regard the standard IEC 62366 – 1, that defines usability as that ‘characteristic of the user interface that facilitates use and thereby establishes effectiveness, efficiency, and user satisfaction in the intended use environment’.

- The **acceptability** is a property of a “complex, adaptive system of interacting components, which in turn influences (and is influenced by) user engagement”¹³. It has to do with the patients’ attitudes towards a new digital health intervention and covers usage intention, actual usage, and satisfaction after usage. The acceptability of the ThrombUS+ device will be assessed both for patients and for the healthcare professionals who would use and apply it (doctors, nursing staff, physiotherapists, other caregivers). Key factors are the safety, comfort and non-intrusiveness of the wearable device, as well as the ease of application and use.
- The **cost-effectiveness** of the device will be assessed within each RUCs to test and assess the economic impact of the intervention. At this stage of building the RUCs, the aim is to have a rough qualitative sense of the potential resource impact of increasing the capacity for early detection of DVT. However, at a later stage of the process, the implementation and technical costs of the device will be calculated and compared to traditional care, using the Monitoring and Assessment Framework for the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing tool (MAFEIP).¹⁴

Importantly, the identification of RUCs and their main functional, technical and regulatory requirements establishes a set of opportunities for the development of the ThrombUS+ device. From these, it is possible that efforts in subsequent phases will concentrate on a more limited and more specific set of cases. However, it is important to stress that this menu should in no way be read as setting out rigid options but rather as a guide to direct subsequent efforts. In particular, it is possible that the technological possibilities and limitations that we will discover in the course of the project will stretch or restrict the options identified at this stage. It is also important to note that no quantitative analysis or clinical risk stratification work was undertaken in this exercise, nor were the RUCs ordered according to any logic of importance. While incidence rates and risk were considered as factors in determining the clustering, it was the functional criteria and socio-technical similarities of the profiles that dominated the construction of the use cases.

3.2.3. Cross-cutting and overlapping factors through literature review

To establish the different factors that crosscut and overlap among the RUCs, we conducted a rapid review of literature to assess the current state of the art in scientific research. The primary objective of this exercise was to understand the most relevant concomitant cross-cutting factors, with relevance due either to their prevalence, or to the increased risk generated by their presence together alongside the RUCs. The secondary objective was to expand upon the evidence gathered during the previous activity and fill in the gaps observed during the RUCs building process.

Table 3. Keywords used for database search. (Source: Authors’ elaboration)

Keywords		
Age	DVT comorbidities	DVT risk assessment
Acute/subacute risk factors	Provoked/Unprovoked VTE	Basal risk factors
Deep Vein Thrombosis	Venous thromboembolism (VTE)	Genetic risk factors
DVT/VTE risk factors	DVT/VTE concurrent conditions	DVT pathophysiology

¹³ Perski, O., & Short, C. E. (2021). Acceptability of digital health interventions: Embracing the complexity. *Translational Behavioral Medicine*, 11(7), 1473-1480. <https://doi.org/10.1093/tbm/ibab048>

¹⁴ The MAFEIP tool measures cost effectiveness and makes impact assessments of ICT health and care solutions. The main outcome of the tool is the Quality-of-Life Years of Patients (QALY). The MAFEIP aims to estimate the outcomes of a large variety of social and technological innovations, by providing an early assessment of the likelihood that interventions will achieve their anticipated impact. In addition, the cost effectiveness analyses with the MAFEIP-tool also helps to identify the drivers of an intervention’s effectiveness or efficiency in order to guide further design, development or evaluation. Therefore, MAFEIP represents a clear support to the decision-making process for HTA.

Pulmonary embolism (PE)	Intrinsic risk factors	Extrinsic risk factors
Risk factors scores	DVT/VTE concurrent illnesses	Epidemiological factors

The first step of the rapid review consisted in a snowballing of academic literature starting from the many papers provided by the clinical partners during the patient profiling exercise. This entailed the identification of relevant papers and sources of information due to its citation frequency in the initial set of papers, or due to the high relevance of the topics covered in the paper. Overall, 91 scientific papers were gathered thanks to the input provided by academic partners and were used for the initial snowballing (Annex 2 - Step 1 Literature References). Subsequently, the research team enriched the initial selection of papers with a traditional search carried out on databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus. This activity was intended as a supplement to the snowballing exercise, and therefore did not follow systematic principles. A set of keywords was established and inserted in the aforementioned databases. Table 3 provides an indicative list of the keywords used (in combination).

The exercise yielded a significant number of concurrent factors and conditions that increase the risk of DVT. The results, that is the list of all the factors and conditions that were identified, is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Cross-cutting risk factors and concurrent conditions. (Source: Authors' own elaboration)

Cross-cutting risk factors and concurrent conditions		
Age	Trauma	Hospitalization
Gender	Surgery duration	Smoking
Immobility/Limited mobility	Varicose veins	Adiposity/Body Mass Index (BMI)
Alcohol consumption	Non-O blood group	Atrial fibrillation
Use of oral contraceptives	Fibrinogen	Cerebral infarction
Personal/family history of DVT/blood clots	Puerperium	Hormone replacement therapy
Cholesterol	Immunodeficiency	Hormonal therapies
Venous catheters	Venous insufficiencies	
Inherited and acquired conditions/disorders (i.e., factor V Leiden mutation, prothrombin gene mutation, protein C and S deficiency, antithrombin deficiency, dysfibrinogenemia, factor XII deficiency, hyperhomocysteinemia, hypercoagulation, Antiphospholipid Antibody Syndrome (APLS), prothrombotic mutations)		
Chronic cardiac conditions (i.e., atherosclerosis, heart failure, hypertension, dyslipidemia)		
Chronic renal conditions (i.e., chronic kidney disease, renal transplant, nephrotic syndrome, microalbuminuria)		
Chronic hematological conditions (i.e., polycythemia vera, paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria, hyperhomocysteinemia)		
Chronic rheumatological conditions (i.e., Behcet disease, rheumatoid arthritis, systemic lupus erythematosus, antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies-associated vasculitis)		
Chronic gastrointestinal conditions (i.e., inflammatory bowel disease)		
Chronic infections (i.e., sepsis, coronavirus disease 2019, tuberculosis)		
Chronic respiratory conditions (i.e., asthma, obstructive sleep apnea, respiratory failures)		
Chronic endocrine conditions: (i.e., polycystic ovary syndrome, diabetes mellitus)		

The researchers then selected the most recurring factors and conditions, and the ones described as more relevant and prevalent in the analysed papers. These were grouped together, and a final shortlist was constructed, as presented in Table 5. Out of all the conditions and factors included in the table above, six were mentioned significantly more often than the others, and were generally described as the most relevant in relation to risk of DVT. These are **age, mobility, hospitalisation, surgery duration, history of DVT, and BMI**. Cancer was also very often mentioned as a highly relevant risk factor, but due to its specificity, prevalence, and incidence it was dealt with as a RUC itself (see Figure 6).

Table 5. Most relevant concurrent factors and conditions. (Authors' elaboration).

Factor/condition	Description	Sources
Age	Advancing and older age are associated with an increased risk of DVT.	Anderson & Spencer, 2003; Cushman et al., 2004; Engbers et al., 2014; Gregson et al., 2019; Hong et al., 2012; Sirlak et al., 2012; Yuhua et al., 2019)
Mobility	The level of mobility is a crucial risk factor for the development of DVT. The risk increases as mobility reduces, with the highest risk arising when the patient is completely unable to move.	Bereda, 2022; Blom et al., 2005; Cushman, 2007; Engbers et al., 2014; Oger et al., 2002)
Hospitalisation	Hospitalisation and its length are considered risk factors for DVT development.	Cushman, 2007; Goldhaber, 2010; Heit et al., 2001, 2016; Jordan Bruno et al., 2022; Yuhua et al., 2019)
Surgery duration	Surgery duration influences the risk of developing DVT, with longer surgeries being significantly more dangerous for patients.	Bekelis et al., 2017; Khaldi et al., 2011; Kim et al., 2015; Pence et al., 2020
History of DVT	Inherited or acquired DVT or VTE predisposition, including prior personal events and family history, are significantly associated with an increase of DVT development.	Galanaud et al., 2018; Heit, 2008; McLendon et al., 2024; Mount et al., 2022; Prandoni et al., 2007; Samama, 2000
BMI	Higher body mass increases the risk of DVT, which becomes particularly significant when BMI ≥ 30 kg/m ² .	Abdollahi et al., 2003; Gregson et al., 2019; Severinsen et al., 2009; Wattanakit et al., 2012

The sources supporting the most relevant concurrent factors shortlist are indicated in the table above. Besides this, all other papers identified and consulted in the supplementary literature review that were deemed relevant either for the identification of concurrent factors or to fulfil information gaps needed to build the RUCs are cited throughout this document, so the complete list of literature are provided as references within the text.

3.3. Step 2 – Reference use cases finetuning and validation with experts

To further inform and validate the seven RUCs identified in the previous steps as described in the section above, we conducted a series of in-depth interviews with expert health professionals. This activity aimed to delve deeper into the specific patient needs and characteristics of each use case by leveraging on clinicians' direct experiences. The knowledge and perspectives of actors in direct contact with DVT-related clinical practice provided us with key elements to ensure that the ThrombUS+ device design aligns with real-world clinical requirements and patient scenarios.

A purposive sampling strategy was employed to recruit a diverse and sufficient pool of participants, ensuring the inclusion of healthcare professionals with substantial experience in managing patients at risk for DVT. More specifically, we opted to recruit mostly participants with specific knowledge applied to each RUC, in order to focus the corresponding in-depth interviews on each of them and gather more exhaustive and reliable information.

The ThrombUS+ consortium includes several clinical partners, including hospitals and medical research universities. Due to this significant advantage, the recruitment process started by involving as many expert health professionals as possible directly from the clinical partners of the project. Experts were identified and recruited after direct suggestions from the clinical partners of ThrombUS+. Overall, experts affiliated with GNP (Greece), LSMU (Lithuania), and CSS-IRCCS (Italy) were contacted and recruited for the interviews. Thanks to the variety of clinical partners in the consortium we were able to recruit participants from various healthcare settings, including hospitals, clinics, and research universities, and coming from different geographical and cultural backgrounds, which allowed us to better capture a wide range of perspectives and experiences. The resulting diversity was crucial to validating the RUCs across different clinical environments. Table 6 below summarises the final sample involved in the interview process, highlighting the specialisation of each interviewee, and the specific RUC covered during the interview.

Table 6. Experts health professionals interviewed.

#	Name	Main expertise	RUC	Institution
1	Dr. Elvira Grandone	Obstetrics, Gynaecology, Thrombosis and Haemostasis	Pregnancy and postpartum	CSS-IRCCS
2	Dr. Marius Rimaitis	Anaesthesiology and Neurosurgery	Neurosurgery	LSMU
3	Dr. Karolis Bareikis	Neurosurgery	Neurosurgery	LSMU
4	Dr. Linas Velicka	Vascular surgery and Phlebology	Cardiovascular surgery and risk	LSMU
5	Dr. Themis Mikos	Obstetrics and Gynaecology	Pregnancy and postpartum	GNP
6	Dr. Eusthatios Kenainidis	Hip and knee surgery	Lower limb orthopaedic surgery	GNP
7	Dr. Arunas Gelmanas	Anaesthesiology	Lower limb orthopaedic surgery	LSMU
8	Dr. Neringa Balciuniene	Intensive Care and Neurosurgery	Neurosurgery	LSMU
9	Dr. Dimitrios Dionysopoulos	Oncology	Cancer and oncological treatment	GNP

Participants were contacted via e-mail to schedule an appropriate date and time to carry out the interviews. Concerning the specific process, the interviews followed a semi-structured format, which provided a consistent framework for exploring specific areas of interest while allowing flexibility to probe deeper into relevant topics. Each interview lasted approximately 60 minutes and was conducted via video conferencing, relying on the Microsoft Teams platform. This format facilitated a comprehensive exploration of individual experiences and perceptions related to each use case.

A pre-designed interview guide was utilised, containing open-ended questions to be explored in relation to the seven RUCs (see Annex 3 – Step 2 Expert’s interview guide). These questions were designed to scope:

- **Interviewees` personal expertise:** The interviews started with a brief overview of the expertise and daily tasks of the participant, to better understand their professional relationship with DVT screening, monitoring and treatment.
- **Clinical information:** In this section of the interview, we investigated which one of the concurrent conditions identified previously (See above Cross-cutting and overlapping factors through literature review) was regarded as particularly relevant to the specific use case, due to its general prevalence or the resulting increased risk of DVT.
- **Patient needs:** Here the focus was on patients` needs in the baseline condition (prior to the development of DVT). Information was collected regarding the mobility of the patient, their level of independency, the hospitalisation procedure, the recovery times, and the expected interactions with clinical facilities and staff.
- **Current DVT journey:** This section of the interview was aimed at understanding better the standard patient journey concerning DVT. Specifically, information was gathered on current practices for the screening, treatment, and monitoring of DVT in patients represented by the specific use case.
- **Continuous DVT monitoring:** Participants were asked to share their opinions on the usability and potential added value of continuous monitoring for DVT in the patient journey. This section was aimed at understanding the relevance of a device like the one that the ThrombUS+ project aims to develop to the specific use case.
- **Design:** Finally, participants were asked to hypothetically describe a continuous monitoring device tailored to patients of the specific RUC. Naturally, this was a high-level exercise, but it allowed the collection of important information on key design aspects,¹⁵ such as the most optimal part of the body to cover, the eventual risks of applying continuous compression, the monitoring frequency, etc. Opinions on the foreseen acceptability of the device on both patients and clinicians` side were also gathered in this section of the interview.

Overall, the semi-structured approach adopted allowed for flexibility to delve deeper into unexpected but relevant topics that emerged during the conversations. This feature was crucial for capturing the complexity of clinical practices and patient needs for each use case. However, the variability in the depth and breadth of data collected across different interviews posed a challenge for comparative analysis.

All interviews were recorded with the participants' explicit consent to ensure accuracy in the subsequent reporting and avoid misinterpretation or loss of information. The recordings were then consulted by the researchers to ensure that all key points and arguments were accurately captured and reported. This meticulous reporting process was essential for capturing the nuances of the participants' responses, which is critical for a thorough analysis.

Thematic analysis was employed to identify and analyse patterns within the data. This method involved steps such as the familiarization with the data, generating initial summaries, searching for themes among the summaries, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the final report. Two researchers independently reviewed the recordings and generated notes to ensure the reliability of the findings. The notes were then organized into broader themes and sub-themes related to the seven reference use cases. Any discrepancies between the researchers' analysis were discussed and resolved to ensure consistency. This collaborative approach enhanced the credibility of the analysis and ensured that the themes accurately reflected the data. The thematic analysis was highly effective for identifying and interpreting patterns in the qualitative data collected, providing deep insights into the complex issues related to each use case. Overall, the analysis focused on extracting key themes related to:

¹⁵ During the design of this section of questions, key input was provided by ThrombUS+ partner ComfTech, that suggested some key aspects to inform the design of the ThrombUS+ wearable prototype.

- general contextual information relative to the RUC,
- clinical background information, especially related to concurrent risk triggering factors,
- patients' needs and DVT-screening practices,
- ThrombUS+ potential added value, and
- high-level functional requirements to enhance the acceptability of the design.

In conclusion, the exercise allowed for the collection and analysis of qualitative data that was turned into valuable insights for the identification of the functional requirements and expectations regarding the new wearable device that will be the final outcome of the ThrombUS+ project. These insights will directly inform the design of the device, ensuring it meets the needs of both patients and healthcare providers in various clinical scenarios, and across different potential use cases. By incorporating feedback from a diverse and experienced group of healthcare professionals, the project may achieve a wearable design that is not only clinically effective but also user-friendly and seamlessly integrated into existing clinical workflows for each specific use case.

Although not altering substantially the quality of the data gathered, it is important to note some limitations of the exercise conducted. The most important one is due to the very early stage of the project, as no clear definition of the technical possibilities of the device was yet available. On one side, this allowed us to discuss with the interviewees about potential designs without technical constraints, but on the other side made several questions more difficult to answer accurately, such as those relating to the acceptability of the device. Moreover, the duration of the task allowed us to conduct only a limited number of interviews. This resulted in a possibly non-exhaustive and non-fully representative number of interviews.

The last limitation is a common issue encountered when conducting qualitative interviews, as the lack of comparable data presents significant challenges. Unlike quantitative research, qualitative data is often subjective and context-specific, making it difficult to standardise and compare across different participants. Each interviewee's unique experiences, perspectives and expressions can lead to a wide variety of responses. A careful and nuanced interpretation of such results in this type of research is therefore essential.

3.4. Step 3 – Reference use cases and creation of *Personas*

Based on the above, seven RUCs, seven user *Personas* were generated, which are presented in the following section (Results: Reference Use Cases and *Personas*). Since the rationale for the former was explained in the previous subsections, what remains to be explained is the reasoning behind the *Personas*.

Personas are intended to describe in clear language suitable for all audiences how a user may interact in each case with the envisioned device, identifying the particular functional requirements. Each *Persona* tells the story of a single, specific hypothetical/fictitious person representing a segment of the user population, whose journey as a potential ThrombUS+ user and its interactions with other actors is explained in a simplified way.

Along with the use cases, *Personas* are aimed to aid technical developers, deployers and users of the ThrombUS+ device to understand the needs of the key stakeholders/beneficiaries and the functionalities of the product, thereby enhancing its development and the patient's and healthcare professional's acceptance, as well as its regulatory approval and commercialisation.

Individual subject to recent trauma and surgery. Lionel is a 66-year-old retired athlete. To stay in good shape, he does some light physical exercise every morning, and completes his routine with a fast-paced walk together with his friends Armando and Diego around the block of houses where they all live. One day, while going out for his daily walk, he misses the last step of the staircase in front of the main door of his home, and by falling on the concrete he fractures his hip. He is rushed to the hospital to proceed with surgery, but a recent incident involving a bus flipping over in the city centre overflowed the hospital with patients in need of urgent surgery. All the surgeons are extremely busy, and the waiting times for Lionel's surgery keep growing, forcing him to stay in bed, without the possibility to move around, for several days. With the ThrombUS+ device, doctors can constantly monitor the risk of DVT and intervene with anticoagulants as soon as the device notifies them. In this way the risk of undiagnosed DVT due to surgery delay and immobility of the patient is significantly reduced, and the long wait time for the surgery does not pose a too high risk for the safety of Lionel. Once the surgery is successful, Lionel is still forced to stay in bed, at home, for most of the day. The rehabilitation proceeds without significant obstacles, but due to his old age, Lionel gets tired rapidly and spends most of the day laying on the bed or on the couch. Doctors however gave him one ThrombUS+ device, that he wears with the help of his daughter. The ThrombUS+ beeps when it detects the formation of blood clots in the vein, potentially leading to DVT. Thanks to the device, Lionel can easily monitor and notice in advance the eventual emergence of DVT, and he can contact his doctors for additional assistance or care when needed.

Figure 7. Preliminary example of hypothetical Persona using ThrombUS+ device

3.5. Step 4 – Next steps: Integration with regulatory and technical requirements for co-design

As explained in the previous sections, in these first steps of Task 2.1 we have identified the RUCs, i.e. the most significant potential use cases for the ThrombUS+ device. In this deliverable we also describe for each of these RUCs the functional needs from the perspective of potential patients and other users at a high level. Moving forward, in the subsequent Tasks 2.2 and 2.3 of WP 2 the aim is to elucidate, in relation to these RUCs, the technical and regulatory possibilities and requirements, so as to conclude on a common and comprehensive understanding of specifications that the device design will have to consider. As part of the work, we must ensure that these requirements consider social (including, in particular, device acceptability), technical, regulatory, ethical and safety aspects.

The fundamental objective of the first three tasks of WP2 is to build a robust, comprehensive and integrated body of criteria that supports and defines the boundaries for the wearable system co-design process (T2.4) and the technological development of the device components (WP3, WP4, WP5). Indeed, the project foresees at a later stage a work package specifically aimed at the integration of the components at a more advanced stage of development (WP6), a process for which the joint results and limitations identified in WP2 will certainly be considered. Thus, although it exceeds the scope of this deliverable, we consider as a part of Task 2.1 the effective integration of its results with those of the subsequent tasks. Ultimately, the integrated and aligned work of WP2 is key to supporting decision making in the product co-design process by establishing the possibilities and constraints that will have to be taken into account during the designing, development and testing phases.

4. Results: Reference Use Cases and *Personas*

This section presents the results of the process of identifying reference use cases and patient-centred functional criteria for the ThrombUS+ device, based on the activities described in the previous sections. It also presents the *Personas* generated to illustrate and facilitate the understanding of the information collected and systematised in the RUCs.

As referred above, the RUCs are intended to shed light on the most relevant scenarios for the use of the ThrombUS+ device, and to identify for each of them the main functional design requirements to enhance the device's acceptability, utility and cost-effectiveness. The seven RUCs hereby presented are constructed on

the basis of clustered patient profiles with clinical conditions or procedures which were identified as prevalent and linked to a relevant incidence of high-risk DVT. All RUCs stand on the data and literature collected from clinical partners by means of the questionnaire (see above Section 3.2 and below Annex 2 - Step 1 Literature References) and on the in-depth insights provided by the experts interviewed.

The selected RUCs are presented below as follows:

1. Neurosurgery
2. Lower limb orthopaedic surgery
3. Cardiovascular surgery and risk
4. Pregnancy and postpartum
5. Obesity
6. Cancer and oncological treatment
7. Autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders

Importantly, the order in which the RUCs are presented hereinafter *does not* follow any scale of risk or assessment of importance. Moreover, the structure for each RUC's presentation is based on the operationalisation of the three key functional concepts previously introduced –acceptability, utility and cost-effectiveness— for each case. It also builds on the semi-structured format of the expert interviews conducted (Annex 2 - Step 1 Literature References).

Thus, for each of the RUCs, a summary of the scope and main features of the use case, including the encompassed patient profiles as identified in Step 1, is firstly presented. Second, the most relevant risk factors for each baseline clinical condition are reviewed in relation to DVT odds and its potential functional impact. From the results of the literature review (see above Section 3.2.3), particular attention is given to age, mobility, hospitalisation, surgery duration, history of DVT, and BMI. Third, the typical needs of the patients in the corresponding baseline patient journey are presented, as well as the current DVT screening procedures applied, if any. Fourth, the potential functional windows of opportunity and the added value that a device such as ThrombUS+ could provide in the context of the scenario in question are put forward. Fifth and last, the high-level functional criteria identified to optimise the design and its acceptability are reported.

Finally, the seven constructed *Personas* are presented, giving an account in simple language of the respective paradigmatic cases and functional scenarios of each of the RUCs (see below Section 4.8).

4.1. RUC #1 – Neurosurgery

4.1.1. RUC summary

The neurosurgery RUC aims to encompass those cases of patients undertaking different kinds of both elective and urgent neurosurgery and its exposure to DVT or VTE.

The assessment and prevention of DVT and its resulting PE is of great concern among neurosurgeons, as these are regarded as one of the main causes of morbidity and preventable death in neurosurgical patients. It is estimated that in the countries of the EU and other associated states the number of neurosurgeries

reaches a mean of 1,642 per million population per year¹⁶, while the incidence of DVT can reach up to 25% and that of PE a 1.5%-3% with a mortality rate of between 9% and 50%¹⁷.

The reason why DVT risk arises so often in these cases is understood to be very much related to the prolonged general anaesthesia and immobility periods that patients are subject to in neurosurgical procedures. In fact, a linear correlation between the duration of surgery and DVT occurrence has been found while early use of pharmacological prophylaxis seems to reduce the risk of lower-extremity DVT up to a 43%¹⁸. Moreover, mechanical compression methods are considered to be significantly effective^{19,20}. Different surgeries, however, have different incidences of risk, with the incidence for cranial surgeries (7.7%) generally being higher than for spinal procedures (1.5%). In a study of patients undergoing standardized dual modality prophylaxis (unfractionated heparin plus external pneumatic compression), Henwood et al found an overall incidence of 7.4% for proximal DVT and 9.7% including distal DVT for combined spinal/cranial procedures²¹.

The first week after the neurosurgical procedure is regarded as the most critical, as it is the period where most DVT/PE develop. Deaths due to VTE during this period seem to outnumber those due to bleeding, despite anticoagulant treatment²². Importantly however, an earlier initiation of prophylaxis was associated with increased risk of repeated neurosurgery for traumatic brain injury²³, which is one of the neurosurgical cases with highest DVT reported incidence (20% to 90%)²⁴, suggesting that in some cases pharmacological prophylaxis may lead to complications that may be risky for patients for reasons other than DVT.

This RUC encompasses the following patient profiles as identified in Step 1:

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- ¹⁶ Reulen, H.-J., Hide, R. A. B., Bettag, M., Bodosi, M., & Cunha e Sa, M. (2009). A report on neurosurgical workforce in the countries of the EU and associated states. *Acta Neurochirurgica*, 151(6), 715-721. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00701-009-0396-0>
- ¹⁷ Ganau, M., Prisco, L., Cebula, H., Todeschi, J., Abid, H., Ligarotti, G., Pop, R., Proust, F., & Chibbaro, S. (2017). Risk of Deep vein thrombosis in neurosurgery: State of the art on prophylaxis protocols and best clinical practices. *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience*, 45, 60-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2017.08.008>
- ¹⁸ Khaldi, A., Helo, N., Schneck, M. J., & Origitano, T. C. (2011). Venous thromboembolism: Deep venous thrombosis and pulmonary embolism in a neurosurgical population. *J Neurosurg*, Jan;114(1):40-6. <https://doi.org/10.3171/2010.8.JNS10332>.
- ¹⁹ Chibbaro, S., Cebula, H., Todeschi, J., Fricia, M., Vigouroux, D., Abid, H., Kourbanhousen, H., Pop, R., Nannavecchia, B., Gubian, A., Prisco, L., Ligarotti, G. K. I., Proust, F., & Ganau, M. (2018). Evolution of Prophylaxis Protocols for Venous Thromboembolism in Neurosurgery: Results from a Prospective Comparative Study on Low-Molecular-Weight Heparin, Elastic Stockings, and Intermittent Pneumatic Compression Devices. *World Neurosurgery*, 109, e510-e516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2017.10.012>
- ²⁰ Ganau, M., Prisco, L., Cebula, H., Todeschi, J., Abid, H., Ligarotti, G., Pop, R., Proust, F., & Chibbaro, S. (2017). Risk of Deep vein thrombosis in neurosurgery: State of the art on prophylaxis protocols and best clinical practices. *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience*, 45, 60-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2017.08.008>
- ²¹ Henwood, P. C., Kennedy, T. M., & Thomson, L. (2011). The incidence of deep vein thrombosis detected by routine surveillance ultrasound in neurosurgery patients receiving dual modality prophylaxis. *J Thromb Thrombolysis*, 32(2), 209-214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11239-011-0583-8>
- ²² Cote, L. P., Greenberg, S., Caprini, J. A., Stone, J., Arcelus, J. I., López-Jiménez, L., Rosa, V., Schellong, S., & Monreal, M. (2014). Outcomes in Neurosurgical Patients Who Develop Venous Thromboembolism: A Review of the RIETE Registry. *Clinical and Applied Thrombosis/Hemostasis*, 20(8), 772-778. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1076029614532008>
- ²³ Byrne, J. P., Witiw, C. D., Schuster, J. M., Pascual, J. L., Cannon, J. W., Martin, N. D., Reilly, P. M., Nathens, A. B., & Seamon, M. J. (2022). Association of Venous Thromboembolism Prophylaxis After Neurosurgical Intervention for Traumatic Brain Injury With Thromboembolic Complications, Repeated Neurosurgery, and Mortality. *JAMA Surgery*, 157(3), e215794. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamasurg.2021.5794>
- ²⁴ Ganau, M., Prisco, L., Cebula, H., Todeschi, J., Abid, H., Ligarotti, G., Pop, R., Proust, F., & Chibbaro, S. (2017). Risk of Deep vein thrombosis in neurosurgery: State of the art on prophylaxis protocols and best clinical practices. *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience*, 45, 60-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2017.08.008>

- spine surgery,
- craniotomy,
- meningioma,
- malignant brain tumour,
- subarachnoid haemorrhage,
- traumatic spinal cord injury,
- severe traumatic brain injury (with neurologic deficit),
- spontaneous intracerebral haemorrhage,
- neurosurgery and other concurrent conditions.

4.1.2. Risk factors and clinical background

The experts interviewed explained that the Caprini score is the most often employed tool to quantify the risk of DVT and to help doctors identify high-risk patient groups. Key factors to observe include the extent and duration of surgery, age, obesity and high BMI, vascular problems, lung issues, sepsis, infarction, immobilization, pregnancy, central venous catheter, oncological complications, coagulation abnormalities, strokes, and fractures.

Describing levels of mobility for patients in this specific RUC is challenging due to the high variability between different pathologies, associated operations, and individual cases within the same pathology. For instance, brain trauma can be mild, moderate, or severe, each associated with different mobility levels. Generally, severe patients are the least mobile and most at risk of developing DVT. These patients might remain unconscious for extended periods or be unable to make fully conscious decisions, severely impacting their mobility and independence. The degree of consciousness post-operation significantly affects mobility and the risk of developing DVT.

For all types of neurosurgical patients, mobility can only be generalized immediately after the operation. All patients are moved to the ICU until at least the next morning and remain completely immobile during this time. If patients wake up without neurological deficits during this period, they can move in bed but are not allowed to stand until at least the following morning. Once transferred back to the general ward, they are generally mobile again, except in cases where significant neurological disorders prevent full mobility (i.e., in case of haemorrhagic strokes, mobility can be significantly limited for up to two weeks).

4.1.3. Patient's and screening process needs

After all major neurosurgical procedures, patients are moved to the neurosurgical ICU until the morning after the operation, or for longer periods if the patient suffered a severe brain injury. If there have not been major complications, the patient is usually awakened before being transferred to the ICU. During this time, the patient is fully immobilised. They stay in the ICU for the first night and are typically moved to the general ward the next morning, where they quickly regain mobility, unless they still have neurological deficits limiting their movement. Recovery times vary greatly and depend on the patient's preoperative condition. Patients with severe neurological problems may never fully recover and could remain bedridden, significantly increasing their DVT risk. In most elective surgery cases, patients spend their ICU time in bed and are allowed to move only to the bathroom once back in the general ward, gradually increasing mobility with a physiotherapists' help. For non-elective surgeries, the variability is too high to generalize the patient journey.

Throughout the patient journey, there are no routine points for DVT screening or monitoring in the absence of symptoms. This is due to the fact that neurosurgery patients need to be subjected to numerous other concurrent exams, that are prioritised over screening for thrombosis. Monitoring and screening usually begin only when symptoms appear, as risk factors alone are insufficient to initiate the process. Even after recovery,

there is no monitoring performed. If symptoms are detected, the patient is transferred to the radiology department in a wheelchair, where an ultrasound screening is usually performed, typically involving a radiologist. If the patient is found to be DVT positive, a cardiovascular specialist is consulted to decide the most appropriate treatment, including the anticoagulation regimen, duration, and follow-up recommendations.

Pharmacological prophylaxis (anticoagulants) is not generally started until at least 48 hours after surgery. Although, according to the experts interviewed, recent literature suggests that early prophylaxis can reduce the risk of DVT, the increased risk of bleeding makes early anticoagulant use rare. In fact, neurosurgery patients, despite being at a higher risk of DVT, cannot be easily anticoagulated, as bleeding can be fatal and may lead to the repetition of the surgery, which is generally associated with poor outcomes. Consequently, doctors prioritize preventing postoperative bleeding, complicating DVT prevention in neurosurgery patients. This issue is specific to neurosurgery and is not as relevant for other types of surgeries, such as abdominal or lower limb surgeries. In fact, excessive bleeding post-neurosurgery can often be fatal, leading to general guidelines recommending the start of mechanical prophylaxis as soon as possible and anticoagulant prophylaxis as soon as, and only if, it is deemed safe. However, the experts interviewed explained that there is no generally agreed consensus on when it is considered safe to start pharmacological prophylaxis.

4.1.4. ThrombUS+ added value

A continuous monitoring device could help doctors determine which patients can safely rely only on mechanical prophylaxis and which ones absolutely need pharmacological prophylaxis. According to the experts, continuous monitoring should start as early as possible to detect blood clot formation and the emergence of DVT, and continue for several days to assess the risk of pulmonary embolism. This would offer the most significant benefit to patients and the greatest improvement from the baseline.

The length of the surgery, especially if it exceeds four hours, is a significant risk factor for DVT. One expert interviewed explained that it could be useful to explore the device's potential to monitor for DVT during surgery. However, another interviewee disagreed, stating that intraoperative use may not add much value since thrombi form quickly, but take days to become a dangerous embolism. Continuous monitoring post-surgery would be thus more beneficial than monitoring during the surgery. Using the device during surgery could be valuable for scientific purposes, but the most critical period for its use is when the patient is in the ICU. A device that performs continuous monitoring could allow doctors to be notified immediately as a thrombus becomes dangerous enough, and potentially start prophylaxis earlier than usual.

Accurately detecting the optimal time to start prophylaxis is particularly informative and would bring the most added value to neurosurgery patients. As explained, in other types of surgeries, prophylaxis can begin even before the operation to increase safety, but this is not the case for neurosurgery due to the high risk of excessive bleeding. Knowing precisely when clots form and the risk of PE increases can be crucial in determining the optimal time to start prophylaxis avoiding unnecessary complications.

4.1.5. High-level acceptability and design requirements

According to the experts, the main determinant for the device's design should be the patient's neurological status. In many cases, doctors can predict whether severe neurological deficits are likely after surgery.

An ideal design that could bring significant benefits to neurosurgery patients, would be an intermittent compression stocking with integrated ultrasound scanning for DVT. This design could provide the necessary mechanical prophylaxis for neurosurgery patients, reducing the need for risky anticoagulant prophylaxis, and alerting doctors if anticoagulant prophylaxis becomes essential. According to the experts, this solution would decrease the risk of DVT without increasing the risk of bleeding.

A stocking device would be an ideal design also because neurosurgery patients may need to be positioned in various ways or moved frequently. Unlike a bracelet or belt, a stocking stays firm and does not slip away, providing compression consistently. One limitation of this design might be that it could be cumbersome and

hinder mobility during recovery, when the patient main goal should be regaining mobility. According to the doctors interviewed, compression is useful only when the patient is fully immobilized; once they can move, their muscles naturally provide compression. A potential solution could be a modular device that adapts to the patient's needs at different stages of recovery. Most neurosurgery patients could wear such a device on their legs, or other parts of the body, without significant issues, except for potential skin irritation. This can be easily avoided by selecting appropriate fabrics and materials for the stockings.

4.2. RUC #2 – Lower limb orthopaedic surgery

4.2.1. RUC summary

The lower limb orthopaedic surgery RUC aims to cover patient profiles undergoing elective and urgent lower limb orthopaedic surgery, considering as well postoperative periods.

Trauma and bone fractures requiring surgery and immobilization are widely recognized as risk factors for DVT. Major orthopaedic surgeries (hip fracture and hip or knee arthroplasty or replacement) are considered to carry the highest risk of DVT-linked complications, especially when performed on patients with polytrauma, immobilization, advanced age, high BMI or other concurrent factors²⁵. Other orthopaedic surgeries of the lower limb including ankle and lower knee fractures, arthroscopic studies or replacements are also not of negligible risk²⁶. It is noteworthy that the incidence of asymptomatic cases is markedly more significant than symptomatic cases, particularly –but not only– in the major surgery cases indicated^{27,28}.

Without prophylaxis, the overall VTE incidence in medical and general surgery hospitalized patients is estimated to be in the range of 10% to 40%, while it raises up to 40% to 60% in major surgery²⁹. However, The American College of Chest Physicians estimates that LMWH prophylaxis reduces the risk of DVT by 50-60% and PE by two-thirds. Consequently, it estimates a risk of 4.3% risk (for combined symptomatic VTE untreated baseline) during the first 35 days after surgery³⁰.

This RUC encompasses the following patient profiles as identified in Step 1:

- Hip, knees, pelvis replacement surgery
- Hip, pelvis fracture surgery
- Hip, knee arthroplasty

²⁵ Lee, S. Y., H, R., Chung, C. Y., Lee, K. M., Kwon, S. S., Sung, K. H., & Park, M. S. (2015). Incidence of deep vein thrombosis after major lower limb orthopedic surgery: Analysis of a nationwide claim registry. *Yonsei Med J.* <https://doi.org/10.3349/ymj.2015.56.1.139>.

²⁶ Zixuan, L., Chen, W., & Li, Y. (2020). Incidence of deep venous thrombosis (DVT) of the lower extremity in patients undergoing surgeries for ankle fractures. *J Orthop Surg Res, 2020;15(1):294.* <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13018-020-01809-0>

²⁷ Nemeth, B., & Cannegieter, S. C. (2019). Venous thrombosis following lower-leg cast immobilization and knee arthroscopy: From a population-based approach to individualized therapy. *Thrombosis Research, 174*, 62-75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2018.11.030>

²⁸ White, R. H., & Henderson, M. C. (2002). Risk factors for venous thromboembolism after total hip and knee replacement surgery. *Current Opinion in Pulmonary Medicine, 8(5)*, 365.

²⁹ Flevas, D. A., Megaloikononimos, P. D., Dimopoulos, L., Mitsiokapa, E., Koulouvaris, P., & Mavrogenis, A. F. (2018). Thromboembolism prophylaxis in orthopaedics: An update. *EFORT Open Reviews, 3(4)*, 136-148. <https://doi.org/10.1302/2058-5241.3.170018>

³⁰ Falck-Ytter, Y., Francis, C. W., Johanson, N. A., Curley, C., Dahl, O. E., Schulman, S., Ortel, T. L., Pauker, S. G., & Colwell, C. W. (2012). Prevention of VTE in Orthopedic Surgery Patients. *Chest, 141(2 Suppl)*, e278S-e325S. <https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.11-2404>

- Ankles fracture surgery
- Major lower limb orthopaedic surgery

4.2.2. Risk factors and clinical background

Orthopaedic patients are a category already at an elevated risk for DVT, with older age, concurrent diseases, previous thrombosis, and atrial fibrillation further increasing this risk. A consulted expert estimated that these conditions are present in about 80% of lower limb orthopaedic surgery patients. Indeed, the majority of patients that require lower limb orthopaedic surgery are of advanced age, reason why the above-mentioned concurrent conditions are so often found in this kind of patients. The literature suggests that compared to patients aged <49 years, the relative risk of DVT was five times higher in patients aged 50-69 and 10 times higher in patients aged >70 years³¹.

The general older age of orthopaedic surgery patients means that this specific patient group is already facing reduced mobility. It is also for this reason that after orthopaedic lower limb surgery, the primary goal of clinicians is to mobilize patients as soon as possible. Prolonged immobility, which is a severe risk for this patient's group, can lead to several significant complications, including DVT, cognitive dysfunction, and extended rehabilitation times.

In general, orthopaedic patients can be divided into two categories. The first category includes patients who can be easily mobilized, such as those undergoing elective surgeries, day case surgeries, and young patients. These patients are mobilized as soon as possible. The second category consists of trauma patients who, due to severe injuries, cannot be mobilized as quickly. These patients are generally immobilized for extended periods and are at the highest risk for DVT.

4.2.3. Patient's and screening process needs

Elective surgery patients are admitted on the day of their procedure, arriving early in the morning and undergoing surgery generally before 4 PM. After surgery, they spend a short time in the post-anaesthesia unit before being transferred to the general ward. Older patients with concurrent health issues may stay a bit longer and are usually transferred to the general ward early the next morning. Typically, they are discharged a few hours later, though those experiencing significant pain may stay overnight. In contrast, trauma patients undergo surgery as soon as possible and typically remain hospitalized for 2 to 3 days before discharge. Patients with more extensive trauma or multiple fractures may require longer hospital stays, sometimes exceeding 10 days.

Patients in the first group are usually mobilized on the same day as their surgery, typically within 6 hours following hip surgery and 12 to 16 hours following knee surgery. This initial mobilization involves a few steps around the bed and depends on the patient's pain and dizziness levels. Anticoagulant treatment is typically initiated around the same time. The delay in starting prophylaxis for knee surgery patients is due to the higher bleeding associated with these procedures compared to hip surgeries, making it riskier to begin anticoagulant treatment after just 6 hours.

Upon discharge, all patients are referred to a rehabilitation facility where, barring major complications, rehabilitation lasts approximately on average 3 months. At the end of this period, patients typically have a follow-up visit with their doctors and may be prescribed oral anticoagulants for the first month of rehabilitation.

Screening for DVT is typically not conducted unless patients show clear symptoms of the condition. Due to the high risk associated with orthopaedic surgery, anticoagulant prophylaxis is routinely administered, except

³¹ Lee, S. Y., H, R., Chung, C. Y., Lee, K. M., Kwon, S. S., Sung, K. H., & Park, M. S. (2015). Incidence of deep vein thrombosis after major lower limb orthopedic surgery: Analysis of a nationwide claim registry. *Yonsei Med J.* <https://doi.org/10.3349/ymj.2015.56.1.139>

in cases where the risk is deemed low, such as young, healthy individuals undergoing minor procedures. Certain procedures, such as hip and knee replacements, carry higher risks, and almost all patients receive prophylaxis. When DVT cases are detected, a cardiovascular surgeon gets involved and is consulted to decide how to proceed with the treatment.

4.2.4. ThrombUS+ added value

The lack of routine screening is a significant issue, given that, according to the experts interviewed, around at least 10% of lower limb surgeries result in DVT. This means that many cases go undetected and are treated late, if treated at all. Continuous monitoring for DVT with a device could enhance detection rates, facilitating earlier recognition and treatment. Indeed, most patients are not screened for DVT unless symptoms appear, as screening procedures are costly and time-consuming. There is therefore a very important screening and detection gap with respect to the (many) asymptomatic cases. An easy-to-use, efficient continuous monitoring device could thus provide a useful, cost-effective solution.

The device could be used for continuous monitoring as early as one-hour post-operation to maximize monitoring time and early detection. After achieving sufficient mobility, typically within 2 to 3 days for elective surgery patients, the device would be less necessary or required for shorter periods. The first three days post-elective surgery are the critical point in time for the use of the device. Conversely, trauma patients confined to prolonged bed rest would benefit from continuous monitoring throughout their lengthy immobile period.

Additionally, anticoagulant prescriptions typically involve low doses to minimize bleeding risks. Continuous monitoring could help doctors identify patients requiring increased anticoagulation for more effective treatment and prevention of pulmonary embolism. For instance, if an early blood clot formation is detected, an expert suggested that doctors could adjust from a standard 10 mg rivaroxaban dose to a higher 20 mg dose, thereby improving prevention measures.

Finally, it was frequently mentioned throughout the interviews, that during the initial month of rehabilitation, some patients fail to adhere to their anticoagulant regimen despite prescription. As these patients are effectively outpatients at this stage, doctors have limited means to monitor or enforce compliance. Continuous monitoring could also address this gap by detecting DVT presence and alerting doctors to non-adherence to treatment, allowing them to intervene with reminders or other interventions designed to enhance treatment adherence.

4.2.5. High-level acceptability and design requirements

In relation to acceptability, one of the experts consulted emphasised that in cases of lower limb surgery it is important to bear in mind that patients have wounds at the sites where the limb was opened for the procedure. If these wounds are compressed or air circulation is restricted too much, the result can be painful and even counterproductive to the patient's recovery. As such, the device should be as minimally invasive as possible, lightweight and ideally flexible, to allow for mobility.

The consulted specialist suggested that for example a belt-type wearable applied to the thighs, similar to blood pressure measurement devices, could be an alternative option to stockings. The device should take up as little space as possible on the limb and be adaptable to move to different parts, higher or lower, thinner or wider, depending on the site of the surgical wound. According to the expert, standard placement should be on the upper thighs of both legs and allow for mobility. The reason why both legs should be monitored has to do with the fact that the major factor in the development of DVT in these cases is immobility, rather than the operation itself, and haemostasis can occur in both legs at the same time.

In relation to the frequency of scanning, it was suggested that it would be useful to have scans every no less than 12 hours, which is considered a sufficient window of time to intervene. Anyway, it was stated that the more often checks are performed, the better.

4.3. RUC #3 – Cardiovascular surgery and risk

4.3.1. RUC summary

The cardiovascular surgery and risk RUC aims to comprise those patients undertaking cardiovascular surgery and those with cardiovascular risk factors associated with DVT or VTE other than obesity (see RUC #6). This RUC has particular clinical proximity to DVT detection and treatment in itself, given the universe of cases linked to the circulatory system that it covers and the fact that specialists in cardiovascular surgery, angiology or phlebology are those usually involved in the diagnosis and treatment of VTE regardless of the condition or procedure that causes it. For this reason, in this RUC the clinical and functional aspects discussed are applicable to cases originating from reasons beyond cardiovascular surgery or cardiovascular risks per se.

Notwithstanding this, it is worth noting that cardiovascular diseases and risk conditions are the leading cause of death in the EU³², and appear to be associated with the incidence of DVT or VTE risk, although the significance is not consistently defined. For instance, out of a sample of 3 million patients undergoing cardiovascular surgery, a study based on extensive United States patients' data found that 1.62% developed deep venous thrombosis and 0.38% pulmonary embolism³³. Interestingly, another study conducted to assess postoperative DVT for coronary artery bypass surgery with maximally aggressive thromboprophylaxis detected a 13% overall incidence³⁴. For abdominal aortic aneurysm repair, the incidence of symptomatic VTE, and particularly PE, was also found significant in both the short and long term periods³⁵. Moreover, DVT risk was found to increase remarkably in patients requiring re-operation, re-intubation or developing a postoperative urinary tract³⁶. The fact that a large proportion of cardiovascular surgery patients are of advanced age^{37,38} is also a key element to consider in prophylactic decisions and in the development of prevention or early detection methods.

As for the typical cardiovascular risk factors associated with a higher incidence of VTE, there is diverse scientific literature pointing to older age, high BMI, diabetes, hypertension, smoking, low HDL cholesterol

³² Eurostat. (2023). *Cardiovascular diseases statistics* [dataset]. Accessed on June 2024 https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Cardiovascular_diseases_statistics

³³ Khoury, H., Lyons, R., Sanaiha, Y., Rudasill, S., Shemin, R. J., & Benharash, P. (2020). Deep Venous Thrombosis and Pulmonary Embolism in Cardiac Surgical Patients. *The Annals of Thoracic Surgery*, 109(6), 1804-1810. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.athoracsur.2019.09.055>

³⁴ Schwann, T. A., Kistler, L., Engoren, M. C., & Habib, R. H. (2010). Incidence and predictors of postoperative deep vein thrombosis in cardiac surgery in the era of aggressive thromboprophylaxis. *Ann Thorac Surg*, Sep;90(3):760-6, 766-768. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.athoracsur.2010.03.117>.

³⁵ Khan, N. (2021). Risk of symptomatic venous thromboembolism after abdominal aortic aneurysm repair in long-term follow-up of 1021 consecutive patients. *J Vasc Surg Venous Lymphat Disord*, 9, 54-61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvsv.2020.03.016>

³⁶ Aziz, F., Lehman, E., Blebea, J., & Lurie, F. (2018). Postoperative complications after lower extremity arterial bypass increase the risk of new deep venous thrombosis. *Phlebology*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268355517737455>.

³⁷ Gangireddy, C., Rectenwald, J. R., Upchurch, G. R., Wakefield, T. W., Khuri, S., Henderson, W. G., & Henke, P. K. (2007). Risk factors and clinical impact of postoperative symptomatic venous thromboembolism. *Journal of Vascular Surgery*, 45(2), 335-341; discussion 341-342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2006.10.034>

³⁸ Jones, J. M., Loubani, M., Grant, S. W., Goodwin, A. T., Trivedi, U., Kendall, S., & Jenkins, D. P. (2021). Cardiac surgery in older patients: Hospital outcomes during a 15-year period from a complete national series. *Interactive Cardiovascular and Thoracic Surgery*, 34(4), 532-539. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icvts/ivab320>

and high triglycerides, although there is no uniformity regarding relative significance^{39,40,41,42,43}. Despite inconsistencies, older age, adiposity and smoking seem to be the three factors with the most consistent association to VTE among several studies⁴⁴.

This RUC thus encompasses the following patient profiles as identified in Step 1:

- Lower extremity arterial bypass
- Abdominal aortic aneurysm repair
- Popliteal vein aneurysm
- Endovascular aortic aneurysm
- Endovascular aortic aneurysm repair (EVAR)
- Aortic valve replacement
- Cardiac surgery
- Cardiovascular risk factors (including smoking, older age, high BMI, etc.)

4.3.2. Risk factors and clinical background

Among the most relevant concurrent factors for cardiovascular patients age stands out, both because ageing increases the chances of developing variants of thrombosis, and because the average age of such patients is usually high. According to the expert practitioner consulted for this case, the majority of the cardiovascular patients tends to be older than 50 to 60 years old, while approximately 30% are aged 80 years or more. A sensible portion of these patients already arrives in the hospital on a wheelchair or with walking aids, meaning mobility is another significant factor for most cardiovascular patients' care. Moreover, older patients tend to present other comorbidities and often have bones or joints problems.

Concerning mobility and its related functional needs, patients can be classified in three groups. The first group includes cardiovascular elective surgery patients (aortic aneurism, femoral bypass, vascular surgery,

³⁹ Ageno, W., Becattini, C., Brighton, T., Selby, R., & Kamphuisen, P. W. (2008). Cardiovascular risk factors and venous thromboembolism: A meta-analysis. *Circulation*, 117(1), 93-102. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.107.709204>

⁴⁰ Gregson, J., Kaptoge, S., Bolton, T., Pennells, L., Willeit, P., Burgess, S., Bell, S., Sweeting, M., Rimm, E. B., Kabrhel, C., Zöller, B., Assmann, G., Gudnason, V., Folsom, A. R., Arndt, V., Fletcher, A., Norman, P. E., Nordestgaard, B. G., Kitamura, A., ... for the Emerging Risk Factors Collaboration. (2019). Cardiovascular Risk Factors Associated With Venous Thromboembolism. *JAMA Cardiology*, 4(2), 163-173. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2018.4537>

⁴¹ Mahmoodi, B. K., Cushman, M., Anne Næss, I., Allison, M. A., Bos, W. J., Brækkan, S. K., Cannegieter, S. C., Gansevoort, R. T., Gona, P. N., Hammerstrøm, J., Hansen, J.-B., Heckbert, S., Holst, A. G., Lakoski, S. G., Lutsey, P. L., Manson, J. E., Martin, L. W., Matsushita, K., Meijer, K., ... Zakai, N. A. (2017). Association of Traditional Cardiovascular Risk Factors With Venous Thromboembolism: An Individual Participant Data Meta-Analysis of Prospective Studies. *Circulation*, 135(1), 7-16. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.116.024507>

⁴² Wang, H., Rosendaal, F. R., Cushman, M., & van Hylckama Vlieg, A. (2022). Association between cardiovascular risk factors and venous thromboembolism in the elderly. *Research and Practice in Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 6(2), e12671. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rth2.12671>

⁴³ Wattanakit, K., Lutsey, P. L., Bell, E. J., Gornik, H., Cushman, M., Heckbert, S. R., Rosamond, W. D., & Folsom, A. R. (2012). Association between cardiovascular disease risk factors and occurrence of venous thromboembolism. A time-dependent analysis. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 108(3), 508-515. <https://doi.org/10.1160/TH11-10-0726>

⁴⁴ Gregson, J., Kaptoge, S., Bolton, T., Pennells, L., Willeit, P., Burgess, S., Bell, S., Sweeting, M., Rimm, E. B., Kabrhel, C., Zöller, B., Assmann, G., Gudnason, V., Folsom, A. R., Arndt, V., Fletcher, A., Norman, P. E., Nordestgaard, B. G., Kitamura, A., ... for the Emerging Risk Factors Collaboration. (2019). Cardiovascular Risk Factors Associated With Venous Thromboembolism. *JAMA Cardiology*, 4(2), 163-173. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2018.4537>

etc.). By default, this group is almost fully mobile, being the only significant restrictions to mobility generally observed right after the operation. If for example the treatment is related to venous problems (i.e. varicose veins), many cases are treated with simple and quick procedures, which raise almost no complications related to immobility (aside of age-related). The second relevant group includes acute patients that usually present complex or advanced diseases and complications, such as acute ischemia, generally located in the arteries. These patients do not tend to have significant mobility issues (again excluding age-related), and usually are fully immobile only right after surgery for a time period ranging from 1 to 3 days, which depends on several factors such as pain and fatigue. Finally, the third group is that of acute or critical patients whose condition foresees an amputation. These patients are at a higher risk of developing DVT as they can spend significant time fully immobilised, depending on the type of amputation performed. Notably, all three categories of patient get by default anticoagulant prophylaxis to reduce the risk of developing DVT. The average (all three groups together) bed rest time for patients undergoing cardiovascular procedures is 4 days.

Aside of age and mobility, other usual DVT-concurrent conditions in cardiovascular patients are coagulation abnormalities, venous and arterial complications, acute limb ischemia arterial, hypercoagulation, and acquired or inherited thrombophilia. In particular, it was mentioned that the proportion of oncological patients in DVT is steadily increasing, and that cancer is nowadays considered in clinical practices as one of the most relevant DVT-triggering factors. High BMI or obesity were also identified as factors of importance in DVT assessment. The expert consulted indicated that other surgical procedures (orthopaedical, trauma, abdominal, neuro) used to be more relevant, but that the increased practice of using pharmacological prophylaxis by default has significantly lowered the incidence.

4.3.3. Patient's and screening process needs

According to the expert interviewed for this case, a key clinical difference in the DVT-risk assessment of patients coming to cardiovascular clinicians' care has to do with whether they are in-patients or out-patients, a difference that also impacts the patients' journey.

In-patients are by default screened via ultrasound before surgery and given heparin and other anticoagulants, making it less likely that they will develop DVT. These patients are not screened after surgery unless DVT symptoms emerge (i.e. swollen legs) in the days right after, in which case another ultrasound is performed. If DVT is detected, they are prescribed anticoagulants. Importantly, the level of mobility is a key aspect that determines the level of risk of thrombosis and therefore the prescription and duration of anticoagulation therapy for these patients. The average in-patient journey usually lasts around 6 days, then they are discharged, and in most complex cases sent to rehabilitation, where they are encouraged to ambulate to recover while reducing the risk of DVT. Even at this stage usually anticoagulants are still given to the patient, and generally another check for DVT is performed after 3 months.

On the other hand, out-patients are usually received into the ward or referred from other clinical departments (such as oncology, primary care or after other types of elective surgery) and often have DVT symptoms or a primary diagnosis, indicating they are at a higher risk of DVT or PE. These patients are screened for DVT as soon as possible by means of ultrasound and eventually complemented via D-dimer.

In both types of patients, the legs are generally scanned, which corresponds to the literature indicating that the vast majority of thrombi are generated there. For instance, in a study on cardiac surgery with thromboprophylaxis Schwann et al⁴⁵ found that below-knee DVTs (78%) occur far more frequently than above-knee DVTs (22%), and DVTs ipsilateral (60%) to SVG harvest sites were twice as likely as those contralateral (32%) to harvest site. The preponderance of DVTs localized to the calf veins was estimated to range between 82% to 93%. However, if the symptoms appear elsewhere (e.g. the arm), then that other site

⁴⁵ Schwann, T. A., Kistler, L., Engoren, M. C., & Habib, R. H. (2010). Incidence and predictors of postoperative deep vein thrombosis in cardiac surgery in the era of aggressive thromboprophylaxis. *Ann Thorac Surg, Sep;90(3):760-6, 766-768*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.athoracsur.2010.03.117>.

is scanned. The main focus is put on checking arteries, to assess for eventual aneurisms, but if there is suspicion of a venous disease then the screening is concentrated on the veins. The ultrasound screening is performed routinely only once and is considered accurate enough for this type of patients. However, if it has negative result and there is still suspicion of DVT as symptoms do not attenuate, then a D-dimer test is performed. As stressed by the consulted expert, in case of doubt the hyperdiagnostic side is preferred.

Thus, anticoagulation is prescribed to all symptomatic patients except to those with bleeding complications, in which case the decision is taken on a case-by-case basis. Moreover, if DVT is detected and the patient is mobile, ambulatory treatment is recommended to avoid immobility as much as possible, thus helping prevent the propagation of the thrombus. However, as discussed above, the high average age and limitations in terms of independence and mobility of a large proportion of patients limit this preventive option.

4.3.4. ThrombUS+ added value

Firstly, given that ultrasound studies are not yet fully reliable to detect DVT and considering that a significant proportion such cases are asymptomatic, a technological development that would enhance early detection rates by scanning with greater sensitivity or frequency would be beneficial in itself, as it would thus help reducing the most dangerous complications. Such continuous screening/monitoring could be especially impactful in those patients under intensive care, with elevated inflammation or undergoing long immobilization periods as a result of high-risk related settings, such as repeated or long surgeries, open belly surgeries, etcetera. If the device were automatic, it would be sufficient for it to perform a scan every 4 hours on this type of patients.

For if the device could achieve levels of sensitivity comparable or better than standard ultrasound scans and require less time and/or human resources to operate (from nurses, technicians or physicians), the value added to the diagnostic process could be considerable. In the best-case scenario, it could reduce the number of ultrasound studies and save nurses' time. In addition, if the device allowed for quick scans, it could be useful to perform routine scans on any patient (improving detection of asymptomatic cases) or to stratify outpatients or patients coming from other departments with symptoms.

4.3.5. High-level acceptability and design requirements

In order to ensure acceptability to health professionals, it is essential that the device does not represent an additional time cost, risk or complexity disproportionately greater than the current procedure - obviously in relation to the benefit in terms of detection that it could provide. It is therefore key that the device is as self-sufficient as possible. The expert consulted maintained that if the patient could sit or lie down with the device in place, for a period during which he or she would not require attention from medical staff except for, for example, the fitting (which should also be simple), health professionals would welcome such a technology.

In relation to patients, it was emphasised that the device should be comfortable and should avoid both excessive pressure (which may cause pain or have contraindicated implications) and skin irritation or other reactions that cause discomfort. It is also important to bear in mind that a large proportion of conscious patients tend to feel anxious about any procedure performed, so that comfort, time of use and the reactions that the device may generate in the body can create barriers to acceptability.

In relation to design, the interviewee noted the possible suitability of a stocking-shaped or similar design. Since many surgeries are bilateral, it would be preferable to monitor both legs. Also, adding anti-embolism compression to the device could be of interest, as it could be especially useful for those patients who cannot be anticoagulated and are therefore at higher risk (such as many neurosurgery patients).

However, while the legs are the most relevant site for scanning possible DVT, the design needs to take into consideration that many of cardiovascular surgery patients have wounds on the legs or have swollen legs as a result of the operation, suggesting that excessive pressure or irritation should be avoided. What is more, for certain cases the application of continuous compression is expressly contraindicated as it could lead to serious complications (e.g. in peripheral arterial disease or low arterial flow patients).

4.4. RUC #4 – Pregnancy and postpartum

4.4.1. RUC summary

The pregnancy and postpartum RUC encompass both the woman's pregnancy period as well as the postpartum period (up to approximately six weeks after the delivery of the baby).

Despite birth rates reduction decreasing across the years, in 2022 the total fertility rate in the EU was of 1.46 live births per woman⁴⁶, leading to 3.88 million children born in the EU. Notably, the mean age of women at childbirth in the EU continued to rise between 2001 and 2022, from an average of 29.0 years old to 31.1 years old. The same trend can be observed for the mean age of women at birth of the first child during the same period in the EU, from a value of 28.8 years old in 2013 (the first year for which the EU value is available) to 29.7 years old in 2022. In addition, near half (46.3 %) of the children born in the EU in 2022 were first-born children⁴².

Among pregnant woman, the incidence of DVT in Europe reaches to 1-1.5 of every 1000 deliveries. In spite of these absolute low risks, pregnancy-associated VTE (DVT and/or PE) is considered a leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality today^{47,48}. There are specific concurrent conditions and points in time that substantially increase the risk of DVT. For instance, VTE incidence increases to 2.3 of every 1000 deliveries if coming from a pregnancy after assisted reproductive techniques, while increases up to fourfold following caesarean sections (as compared to vaginal delivery)^{49,50}. In relation to critical time points, the risk of VTE reaches its highest in the third trimester of pregnancy and during the first six weeks after delivery⁵¹.

This RUC encompasses the following patient profiles as identified in Step 1:

- natural pregnancy,
- pregnancy after assisted reproductive techniques,
- ovarian hyper stimulation syndrome (OHSS),
- postpartum period,
- post C-section.

⁴⁶ Eurostat. (2022). *Fertility statistics* [dataset]. Retrieved on June 2024. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Fertility_statistics

⁴⁷ Bates, S. M., Rajasekhar, A., Middeldorp, S., McIntock, C., Rodger, M. A., James, A. H., Vazquez, S. R., Greer, I. A., Riva, J. J., & Bhatt, M. (2018). American Society of Hematology 2018 guidelines for management of venous thromboembolism: Venous thromboembolism in the context of pregnancy. *Blood advances*, 2(22), 3317-3359.

⁴⁸ Heit, J. A., Kobbervig, C. E., James, A. H., Petterson, T. M., Bailey, K. R., & Melton, L. J. (2005). Trends in the incidence of venous thromboembolism during pregnancy or postpartum: A 30-year population-based study. *Ann Intern Med*, 143, 697-706.

⁴⁹ Blondon, M., Casini, A., Hoppe, K. K., Boehlen, F., Righini, M., & Smith, N. L. (2016). Risks of Venous Thromboembolism After Cesarean Sections: A Meta-Analysis. *Chest*, 150(3), 572-596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chest.2016.05.021>

⁵⁰ Goualou, M., Noumegni, S., Moreuil, C. de, Guillou, M. L., Coninck, G. D., Hoffmann, C., Robin, S., Morcel, K., Moigne, E. L., Tremouilhac, C., Merviel, P., Mao, R. L., Leroyer, C., Bouée, S., Couturaud, F., & Tromeur, C. (2023). Venous Thromboembolism Associated with Assisted Reproductive Technology: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 123(3), 283-294. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0042-1760255>

⁵¹ Pomp, E. R., Lenselink, A. M., Rosendaal, F. R., & Doggen, C. J. M. (2008). Pregnancy, the postpartum period and prothrombotic defects: Risk of venous thrombosis in the MEGA study. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis: JTH*, 6(4), 632-637. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1538-7836.2008.02921.x>

4.4.2. Risk factors and clinical background

The experts interviewed indicated several scenarios with relation to pregnancy and postpartum where the risk of DVT and PE is higher according to practice and scientific evidence. To begin, in relation to pregnancy, it was pointed out that the risk of developing DVT progressively increases after each pregnancy, becoming significantly higher after the fourth. Moreover, multipara and pregnancies achieved through assisted reproduction techniques, such as *in-vitro* fertilization, were said to be also associated with a heightened risk of DVT. Furthermore, pregnancy complications such as high fluid retention, infections and preeclampsia significantly raise the risk of developing DVT.

Maternal age was also indicated to be a critical factor, with older women facing a greater risk of DVT and PE compared to younger women. Other concurrent factors such as high BMI or obesity, smoking habits and the presence of leg varicosities also contribute to elevating the risk.

The fact that women tend to reduce their mobility significantly (and most abruptly in the first three months of pregnancy as a result of fear of spontaneous abortion) was mentioned as a key point, despite this increased risk of DVT. One interviewee therefore noted the practice of recommending the use of preventive compression stockings yet acknowledged low adherence.

In low-risk pregnancies women remain in average three days hospitalized (for vaginal deliveries), mostly due to baby-related check-ups. During this period, women are usually independent to move and not forced to rest in bed or remain immobile, thereby reducing immobility-associated risks. Other cases may have more variable hospitalisation-settings (and related risks) depending on the type of complications.

4.4.3. Patient's and screening process needs

Usually, pregnant women interact with clinicians (obstetricians) for routine checks around 8 to 10 times in the pre-natal period. The first interaction is crucial because is the one in which doctors assess the risk of DVT. If the patient is considered of high risk (due to symptoms or concurrent conditions such as pain in the left leg, lower abdominal pain, varicose veins, anaemia, obesity, immobility etc.) a screening for DVT is usually performed. If due to the symptoms or after screening the patient is considered of moderate risk, the most usual is to start prophylaxis (low molecular weight heparin - LMWH) for around three months. In women where such prophylaxis is not prescribed antenatally, graduated compression stockings are usually recommended⁵². If the risk is medium or high, patients can be hospitalised, and more in-depth analysis and screenings are performed.

Once women enter labour, they get hospitalised to deliver the baby. After giving birth and if there are no further complications, patients stay hospitalised an average of three days (for vaginal delivery). During these days, patients are mostly able to fulfil all their basic needs independently. The situation is different in C-Section deliveries, as patients usually need to be immobilised for at least 12 hours. When mobility is re-achieved, in most cases patients still struggle to walk around fully independently for several hours. Normal mobility is generally achieved only a couple days after delivery. For this kind of patients, low molecular weight heparin thromboprophylaxis is generally prescribed. In certain complicated cases and complications (of lower frequency), patients may need to be immobilised and forced in bed for several days. For instance, patients at risk of premature delivery are immobilised and given drugs to delay the delivery. Other complications include, among others, post-partum haemorrhage (PPH), surgery during pregnancy, preeclamptic patients, and patients with neurological problems. It is important to note that in the case of PPH (which is the leading cause of maternal mortality worldwide) it is not possible to use LMWH thromboprophylaxis, which especially after blood transfusions, increases the possibility of VTE.

⁵² Greer, I. A. (2003). Prevention of venous thromboembolism in pregnancy. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Haematology*, 16(2), 261-278. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1521-6926\(02\)00095-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1521-6926(02)00095-6)

Overall, according to the expert interviewees, approximately 45% of deliveries are vaginal and do not present further complications nor mobility limitations, while 55% of deliveries via C-section lead to around 1-3 days of immobilisation and forced bed rest. About 1-2% account for more serious complications that lead to longer immobilisation.

After discharge in average circumstances, a routine check with clinicians is conducted after six weeks. If the woman was not considered of high-DVT risk, it is not usual that further monitoring or screening are performed. However, if there was a prophylaxis treatment ongoing, it generally continues (self-administered) for several weeks after discharge, up to three months depending on the condition.

The consulted clinical partners stressed the high importance to continuously monitoring VTE-related symptoms. In case of moderate to high clinical suspicion or actual diagnosis at some point of the pregnancy or the postpartum periods, the patient may be hospitalised for seven to ten days and receive pharmacologic and/or mechanic prophylactic treatment. Patients in such cases are also scanned via doppler ultrasound and VQ for suspected DVT and PE. Notably, it was highlighted that almost 90% of pregnancy-associated DVT happens on the left side in contrast to non-pregnant situations (55%)⁵³.

4.4.4. ThrombUS+ added value

In cases where there is sufficient suspicion or VTE is detected, there are potential windows of opportunity for a continuous DVT monitoring device applicable to both hospitalised and self-treated patients. This is because, as reported by clinicians, whatever the circumstances and regardless of whether the patient is classified as high or very high risk, it is not possible to continuously monitor the formation of blood clots that may result in VTE, even in high-risk therapy units. In addition, there are very serious and prevalent conditions (such as PPH) in which it is not possible to use thromboprophylaxis and which result in an increased risk of VTE. Therefore, the possibility of continuously scanning and alerting for possible indicators of DVT could therefore allow earlier and more effective detection of the clinical event, allowing better utilisation of clinical resources.

Furthermore, once the patient is fully discharged and goes home, the contact is most often lost. If the device could be used outside clinical settings (for instance at home or during flight travel), it could be used preventively for moderate risk cases, thus also allowing to both follow up and better understand prophylactic self-treatment outcomes. Finally, a continuous monitoring system would allow clinicians to better understand VTE re-occurrence.

4.4.5. High-level design and acceptability requirements

Both the experts and the literature consulted point out that in addition to LMWH prophylaxis, the use of graduated elastic compression stocking is encouraged, indicating that physical and non-pharmacological devices to prevent VTE events are already welcome in current practice. The potential of a device such as ThrombUS+ to prevent avoidable maternal deaths or long-term health consequences for women, with VTE being one of the leading causes of such outcomes, means that it could be highly valued if it can increase early detection rates and acceptance in use.

Regarding the potential functionalities, the experts consulted pointed out that a possible device could pick up key signs such as saturation, pulse rate, and respiratory rate, and send an alarm to doctors as soon as DVT-related anomalies would be detected. This information could be monitored constantly (in clinical or external settings) to provide real-time alerts and allow to act as soon as DVT-related indicators are detected. From a functional point of view, the importance of simplicity of use (to be easily deployed by nurses and patients on their own) was highlighted. It was further noted that the device should be able to store the

⁵³ Greer, I. A. (2003). Prevention of venous thromboembolism in pregnancy. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Haematology*, 16(2), 261-278. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1521-6926\(02\)00095-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1521-6926(02)00095-6)

information gathered in the past 24 hours at least, so that after receiving an alarm doctors could assess the data and take an informed decision.

Since, as mentioned, 90% of the cases occur on the left leg, the design of the wearable could be thought of in relation to that point of the body. Depending on what is technically possible and considering primarily the comfort of the patients, it was indicated that the device could be in the form of a stocking, or a strap, belt or band.

In terms of acceptability, it was highlighted important to consider that continuous compression, although not specifically dangerous for these cases (which is why compression stockings are employed), can nevertheless be very uncomfortable or painful if applied continuously. This could affect adherence, especially outside of clinical settings. For in-hospital settings, mechanical compression (such as intermittent pneumatic calf compression) is considered of value during C-section and immediately after delivery⁵⁴. It is also very important to take into account that pregnant women are more likely to suffer from overheating, in addition to their general discomfort due to reduced mobility. Therefore, the wearable device's shape and material should be light and allow for proper breathability. Finally seeking interoperability with other electronic devices, including smartphones, could make it more user friendly and easier to accept for patients.

4.5. RUC #5 – Cancer and oncological treatment

4.5.1. RUC summary

The cancer and oncological treatment RUC covers both patients with active cancer and patients subject to oncological treatment, as both the malignancy in itself and the therapeutics modalities are known to significantly increase VTE risk.

Thrombosis, after cancer itself, is the leading cause of death in cancer patients as well as a major complication in their treatment⁵⁵. At the same time, cancer is regarded as the most important and most frequent risk factor for the development of VTE, especially when combined with major surgery⁵⁶. Depending on the type and stage of cancer and the type of treatment, it is estimated that the incidence of VTE in cancer patients can be as high as 20%, overall resulting in significantly decreased survival. VTE risk rates are the highest in pancreatic, brain, myeloproliferative and stomach cancer^{57,58,59}. In addition to the risks associated with cancer malignancy per se, cancer patients are subjected to therapeutic treatments that carry a higher risk of

⁵⁴ Greer, I. A. (2003). Prevention of venous thromboembolism in pregnancy. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Haematology*, 16(2), 261-278. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1521-6926\(02\)00095-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1521-6926(02)00095-6)

⁵⁵ Lutsey, P. L., & Zakai, N. A. (2023). Epidemiology and prevention of venous thromboembolism. *Nature Reviews Cardiology*, 20(4), 248-262. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41569-022-00787-6>

⁵⁶ Heit, J. A., Spencer, F. A., & White, R. H. (2016). The epidemiology of venous thromboembolism. *Journal of Thrombosis and Thrombolysis*, 41(1), 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11239-015-1311-6>

⁵⁷ Kessler, C. M. (2009). The Link Between Cancer and Venous Thromboembolism: A Review. *American Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 32(4), S3. <https://doi.org/10.1097/COC.0b013e3181b01b17>

⁵⁸ Khorana, A. A., Mackman, N., Falanga, A., Pabinger, I., Noble, S., Agno, W., Moik, F., & Lee, A. Y. Y. (2022). Cancer-associated venous thromboembolism. *Nature Reviews Disease Primers*, 8(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41572-022-00336-y>

⁵⁹ Wun, T., & White, R. H. (2009). Venous Thromboembolism (VTE) in Patients with Cancer: Epidemiology and Risk Factors. *Cancer Investigation*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07357900802656681>

thrombophilia such as immunosuppressive or cytotoxic chemotherapy, angiogenesis inhibitors, adjuvant hormonal manipulation, or the use of central venous access devices^{60,61,62}.

Remarkably, despite the incidence of DVT or VTE in cancer patients, the recognition and relevance of prevention of these scenarios is still perceived to be low. A survey conducted by the European Cancer Patient Coalition (ECPC) found that less than 30% of cancer patients surveyed were aware of their increased risk of developing some form of thrombosis, while 26% of patients reported that they had become aware of cancer-associated thrombosis only after developing a blood clot⁶³.

This RUC encompasses the following patient profiles as identified in Step 1:

- cancer,
- chemotherapy,
- protein kinase inhibitors,
- antiangiogenic therapy,
- immunotherapy,
- central venous catheter.

4.5.2. Risk factors and clinical background

Cancer patients face unique challenges due to the variety of cancer types, disease volumes, cancer sites, comorbidities, medication issues, backgrounds, and daily activities they face. While these factors are also relevant in other diseases, they are particularly significant in oncological patients. Consequently, estimating the risk for DVT is complex, and despite a generally high incidence in the general patient population, DVT risk in cancer patients must be assessed individually. In general, cancer patients are at increased risk due to major surgeries, long periods of immobilisation and hospitalisation⁶⁴. Some general key factors influencing DVT risk include age, mobility, comorbidities, general frailty, obesity, and high BMI. Previous thrombosis is often considered a critical risk factor, often prompting immediate DVT screening. Subclinical cases of DVT, which do not show symptoms, are also common.

Metastasis, operations in the brain or spinal cord, and fatigue with subsequent reduced mobility after chemotherapy are primary causes of DVT in cancer patients. Central nervous system cancers or those affecting the brain dramatically increase DVT risk. Lung cancers involving venous system compromise (e.g., adenopathy), as well as stomach and pancreatic cancers, also significantly elevate such risk.

Mobility levels vary significantly based on the cancer type and patient characteristics. Generally, cancer treatment involves several periods of reduced mobility. For instance, patients undergoing chemotherapy may

⁶⁰ Abdol Razak, N., Jones, G., Bhandari, M., Berndt, M., & Metharom, P. (2018). Cancer-Associated Thrombosis: An Overview of Mechanisms, Risk Factors, and Treatment. *Cancers*, 10(10), 380. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers10100380>

⁶¹ Heit, J. A., Spencer, F. A., & White, R. H. (2016). The epidemiology of venous thromboembolism. *Journal of Thrombosis and Thrombolysis*, 41(1), 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11239-015-1311-6>

⁶² Kessler, C. M. (2009). The Link Between Cancer and Venous Thromboembolism: A Review. *American Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 32(4), S3. <https://doi.org/10.1097/COC.0b013e3181b01b17>

⁶³ Falanga, A., Girvalaki, C., Monreal, M., Easaw, J. C., & Young, A. (2022). How well do European patients understand cancer-associated thrombosis? A patient survey. *Cancer Treatment and Research Communications*, 31, 100557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctarc.2022.100557>

⁶⁴ Abdol Razak, N., Jones, G., Bhandari, M., Berndt, M., & Metharom, P. (2018). Cancer-Associated Thrombosis: An Overview of Mechanisms, Risk Factors, and Treatment. *Cancers*, 10(10), 380. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers10100380>

be bedridden for four to five days post-treatment. Complications during the treatment, such as the development of infections may lead to lengthy periods of hospitalization, further limiting mobility. Conversely, it is not uncommon for some patients to respond well to treatment, sometimes even resulting in increased mobility.

4.5.3. Patient's and screening process needs

Screening for DVT in cancer patients is rarely performed due to the already extensive number of tests and screenings required during their limited interactions with doctors. However, an unplanned screening might be initiated if there is a personal history of DVT, as this presents the highest risk. DVT is most often observed at two points in a cancer patient's journey: at the initial presentation and diagnosis, particularly if decreased mobility is a factor, and during the first cycle of chemotherapy due to side-effects causing reduced mobility. Occasionally, DVT is detected later during a routine computed tomography (CT) scan, generally not due to specific symptoms but due to the hypercoagulability associated with cancer.

If DVT is detected during a random scan or through evident symptoms, the patient is hospitalized and treated. Once treatment concludes, no further monitoring is performed. When hospitalized, most cancer patients receive prophylactic treatment by default, unless they have concurrent bleeding, which is the primary reason they might not receive it. Consequently, it is rare for DVT to develop as a result of hospitalization alone.

Post-discharge, treatment usually continues for at least six months, often longer. The expert interviewed estimated that around 35% of outpatients receive prophylactic treatment at home, based on doctors' risk assessments, and particularly if the cancer is located in high-risk areas like the brain or pancreas. Determining when to stop the prophylactic treatment is often challenging for doctors, which leads to cases where the treatment extends for years, often becoming burdensome for the patient, and potentially leading to reduced treatment adherence and subsequent increased risk of DVT.

Overall, patient interactions with doctors and clinical facilities vary based on individual conditions, typically occurring once or twice a month. Full hospitalization (not specific to DVT) happens only when the patient's condition becomes critical and cannot be managed as an outpatient.

4.5.4. ThrombUS+ added value

Continuous monitoring could add significant value in several ways. It could aid in the early detection of asymptomatic DVT, as currently no specific DVT screening is performed to prioritize other more pressing exams. A device that requires minimal operator intervention and can continuously monitor the patient would enable DVT checks in settings where none exist.

Additionally, it could improve the understanding of outpatients' conditions after discharge when they are on prophylactic treatment. Continuous monitoring could help assess the treatment's effectiveness and determine the optimal time to increase or halt it, alleviating the burden on patients who endure long-term prophylactic treatment. This device would also assist doctors in deciding when to stop treatment, enhancing the patients' quality of life without compromising their safety.

Even patients who have responded well to treatment and regained full mobility, but had prophylaxis during earlier stages, could benefit from continuous monitoring to prevent recurrence. In conclusion, all patients with limited monitoring, such as asymptomatic ones, would particularly benefit, as no baseline screening for DVT is currently performed.

4.5.5. High-level acceptability and design requirements

Most DVT cases occur in the leg, so a leg device would probably be most appropriate. In general, and excluding highly specific cases, there are no particular limitations on placing specific devices on cancer patients' bodies. Since sometimes symptoms are detected in other parts of the body as well, it would be

beneficial to have a device that can adapt to these different areas and monitor for DVT, for example by measuring differences in coagulability.

The device's sensitivity will be crucial in determining how long (during a day) it needs to be worn by the patient. If it functions by comparing values between activity and rest states, and it is therefore designed to be worn almost 24/7, it must be made as comfortable as possible to ensure patients wear it even during sleep. Comfort and ease of use are especially important for cancer patients, who are already fatigued and must adhere to multiple treatments and devices. For a new device to be effective, it must be user-friendly and comfortable to ensure patient adherence.

Given that cancer patients might need to wear the device for months, years, or even for the rest of their lives, depending on the severity of their disease, it is vital to design a device that, alongside not causing discomfort, is very user-friendly and requires the least attention and effort possible from the patient. These universal needs are particularly significant for cancer patients who often use multiple devices and undergo concurrent treatments. Ideally, the device should be able to perform and be 'forgotten' by the patient, by being non-intrusive and not requiring particular attention.

4.6. RUC #6 – Obesity

4.6.1. RUC summary

This RUC is intended to cover for those patients with overweight (BMI > 25 kg/m²) and obesity (BMI > 30 kg/m²) as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO).

Obesity is defined as an excess of body fat and usually described by the body mass index (BMI) which is calculated as the square of weight/height. Obesity is a complex multifactorial disease defined by excessive adiposity and is linked to an increased risk for many noncommunicable diseases (NCDs). Due to unhealthy eating habits and decreased physical activities, obesity has become a worldwide epidemic that is driving increased morbidity and mortality, largely driven by increased cardiovascular risk factors⁶⁵.

Overweight and obesity affect almost 60% of adults and nearly one in three children (29% of boys and 27% of girls) in the WHO European Region (WHO, 2022). Recent estimates suggest that overweight and obesity is the fourth most common risk factor for NCDs in the European Region, after high blood pressure, dietary risks and tobacco. It is also the leading risk factor for disability, causing 7% of total years lived with disability, and obesity is linked to greater morbidity and mortality from COVID-19.

In addition, obese and overweight patients have a higher risk of recurrent DVT episodes compared to non-obese individuals. Obesity was found to double the odds to get VTE and to have the most significant impact in people under 40 years old by increasing their odds fivefold^{66,67}.

This RUC is highly related to RUC #3 (Cardiovascular surgery and risk) and encompasses the following patient profiles as identified in Step 1:

- obesity,

⁶⁵ Powell-Wiley, T. M., Poirier, C. P., Burke, V. C. L. E., Després, J.-P., Gordon-Larsen, P., Lavie, C. J., Lear, S. A., Ndumele, C. E., Neeland, I. J., Sanders, P., & St-Onge, M.-P. (2021). Obesity and Cardiovascular Disease. *Circulation*, 143(21), e984-e1010. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIR.0000000000000973>

⁶⁶ Ageno, W., Becattini, C., Brighton, T., Selby, R., & Kamphuisen, P. W. (2008). Cardiovascular risk factors and venous thromboembolism: A meta-analysis. *Circulation*, 117(1), 93-102. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.107.709204>

⁶⁷ Stein, P. D., Matta, F., & Hughes, M. J. (2016). Home Treatment of Deep Venous Thrombosis According to Comorbid Conditions. *The American Journal of Medicine*, 129(4), 392-397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjmed.2015.10.022>

- overweight,
- high BMI and other conditions.

4.6.2. Risk factors and clinical background

Obesity-driven chronic inflammation and impaired fibrinolysis appear to be major effector mechanisms of thrombosis in obesity. Patients with obesity are less mobile than people with normal weight and are also more often hospitalized because of related symptoms. Obesity is also associated with increased risk in DVT, independently from gender or ethnic groups. The assumption is that the proinflammatory and hypofibrinolytic effects of obesity may be exacerbated by dysregulated expression and secretion of adipokines and microRNAs⁶⁸, which further increase the risk of thrombosis and suggest new potential targets for therapy that are needed to prevent and/or treat it.

In addition, obesity may cause thrombosis through the actions of so-called adipocytokines from adipose tissue (e.g. leptin and adiponectin) and increased activity of the coagulation cascade and decreased activity of the fibrinolytic cascade, increased inflammation, increased oxidative stress and endothelial dysfunction, and disturbances of lipids and glucose tolerance in association with the metabolic syndrome⁶⁹. While the odds of young people (<40) with obesity to get VTE increase fivefold⁷⁰, the use of contraceptives by women with obesity is reported to increase DVT risk almost tenfold⁷¹.

4.6.3. Patient's and screening process needs

Patients with obesity are usually not screened for thrombosis because there is usually a lot of other concurrent symptoms that have a higher priority, such as breathlessness, sleep apnea, joint and back pain, and psychological consequences. Importantly, the symptoms of patients with obesity decrease significantly when the patient follows a lifestyle treatment (and sometimes medication) or change their eating habits. Depending on the level and symptoms of obesity that patients are suffering from, screening of the patients and the probability to develop thrombosis are needed. Furthermore, it will depend on the severity of the other symptoms of the patients, also the level of inflammation is thereby influenced and indirectly decreases the probability to develop thrombosis.

4.6.4. ThrombUS+ added value

The main determinant for specificities in the co-creation of the design of the device would depend on the health status and weight of the patient. In co-creation with the doctor and patient, taking into account also the exact health status and weight of the patient, the most pragmatic and efficient solutions should be established to ensure an effective way to use the ThrombUS instruments in such a way that they do not bother the patients too much. In addition, considering patients with obesity will follow lifestyle treatments to reduce their weight and fat percentage, this will influence wearing the different wearables as well. Therefore, they should be adjustable for these patients.

Intermittent compression stockings with integrated ultrasound scanning for DVT would be an ideal design for patients with obesity, because it would both give mechanical prophylaxis that is needed for these patients, reduce the need for risky anticoagulant prophylaxis, and in the meantime, alert doctors if the

⁶⁸ Kwok, S., Adam, S., Ho, J. H., Iqbal, Z., Turkington, P., Razvi, S., Le Roux, C. W., Soran, H., & Syed, A. A. (2020). Obesity: A critical risk factor in the COVID-19 pandemic. *Clinical Obesity*, 10(6), e12403. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cob.12403>

⁶⁹ Darvall, K. a. L., Sam, R. C., Silverman, S. H., Bradbury, A. W., & Adam, D. J. (2007). Obesity and Thrombosis. *European Journal of Vascular and Endovascular Surgery*, 33(2), 223-233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejvs.2006.10.006>

⁷⁰ Stein, P. D., Beemath, A., & Olson, R. E. (2005). Obesity as a risk factor in venous thromboembolism. *Am J Med*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjmed.2005.03.012>.

⁷¹ Rosano, G. M. C., Rodriguez-Martinez, M. A., Spoletini, I., & Regidor, P. A. (2022). Obesity and contraceptive use: Impact on cardiovascular risk. *ESC Heart Fail*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ehf2.14104>.

situation gets critical and anticoagulant prophylaxis becomes fundamental. This solution would not increase the risk of bleeding while decreasing the risk of DVT.

Same as for neurological patients, the stocking device would be a preferred design because patients with obesity might follow also a dietary and exercise treatment. Therefore, a stocking design rather than a bracelet or belt, other than allowing for compression, would allow the device to stay firm and not slip away to support the activities of the patients better. One issue with this design however is that, although being extremely useful in the ICU, it might be cumbersome and alter mobility in the subsequent days where the patient should regain mobility. The compression indeed would be useful only when the patient is fully immobilised, because when they are able to move compression is applied naturally by the muscles of the patient moving. A good solution could be a device in stages that can be adapted to the point in time where it is needed, always in collaboration with the patients to understand exact needs and ensure sustainability of the device.

In general, patients with obesity are expected to have no problems on putting a device like this on the legs, except for skin irritation due to infections in skin folds, but that can be avoided by selecting the appropriate materials for the stocking. Furthermore, given that the number of follow-up Doppler ultrasound studies performed in obese patients is significantly higher than in normal weight patients⁷², the use of a device such as ThrombUS+ could reduce costs and facilitate follow-up.

4.6.5. High-level acceptability and design requirements

The acceptability of the instruments and devices will be crucial to understand how long the device would be needed to be worn by the patient suffering from obesity. If, for example, identical to the other disease areas, it works by comparing values between activity and rest states, then it needs to be made as comfortable as possible, so that patients would spontaneously wear it even during sleep.

Comfort and easiness of use of the device needs to be considered, especially for patient suffering from obesity, since they already suffer from several symptoms related to obesity, like fatigue, difficult mobility, difficulties breathing, and have to adhere to multiple different (lifestyle) treatments, and rely on several devices, so when adding a new one it must be easy to use and comfortable to ensure adherence.

Additionally, patients with obesity might need to wear the device for months or years, and in some cases, depending on the characteristics and gravity of the disease, they would have to wear it for the rest of their life when they are not able to treat the disease effectively, alongside other devices and concurrent treatments. This characteristic stresses even more the importance of designing a device that is comfortable and does not bother patients with obesity too much because their body is already something that makes life more challenging than for other patients or citizens. Most cases are in the leg so a leg device would be more appropriate, and there are no particular limitations regarding patients with obesity on placing specific devices in specific parts of the body. If other parts of the body present symptoms, it would be interesting to have a device that can adapt to the other parts of the body as well, and if possible, measure differences in coagulability. Considering patients with obesity have a large amount of bodyfat, this is something that needs to be discussed together with the patients and other doctors.

4.7. RUC #7 – Autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders

4.7.1. RUC summary

The autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders RUC aims to cover the set of those patient profiles at risk of DVT due to autoimmune diseases or genetic disorders of various kinds.

⁷² El-Menyar, A., Asim, M., & Al-Thani, H. (2018). Obesity Paradox in Patients With Deep Venous Thrombosis. *Clin Appl Thromb Hemost*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1076029617727858>.

An autoimmune disease is the result of the adaptive immune system mistakenly attacking healthy and functioning body parts, instead of protecting them. There are over 100 known autoimmune diseases. Common ones include lupus, rheumatoid arthritis, Crohn's disease, multiple sclerosis and ulcerative colitis. Autoimmune diseases can affect many types of tissues and nearly any organ in your body⁷³. They may cause a variety of symptoms including pain, tiredness (fatigue), rashes, nausea, headaches, dizziness and more. Specific symptoms depend on the exact disease. Autoimmune diseases affect approximately one in ten individuals, and their burden continues to increase over time at varying rates across individual diseases. The socioeconomic, seasonal, and regional disparities observed among several autoimmune disorders in our study suggest environmental factors in disease pathogenesis. The inter-relations between autoimmune diseases are commensurate with shared pathogenetic mechanisms or predisposing factors, particularly among connective tissue diseases and among endocrine diseases⁷⁴.

In general, autoimmunity is characterized by self-reactive immune components and autoimmune disease by autoimmunity plus pathology. Both autoimmunity and autoimmune diseases are dramatically increasing in many parts of the world, most probably as a result of changes in our exposures to environmental factors. Current evidence shows that the developments in our foods, xenobiotics, air pollution, infections, personal lifestyles, stress, and climate change are causing these increases. Nonetheless, autoimmune diseases have a major impact on the individuals and families they affect, as well as on our society and health care costs, and current projections suggest they may soon take their place among the predominant medical disorders globally.

In addition, genetic disorders, such as an inherited tendency to thrombosis also known as thrombophilia, influence the probability to get diagnosed with thrombosis⁷⁵. Antithrombin is a substance in the blood that limits the blood's ability to clot and the primary inhibitor of thrombin, which is required for the development of blood clots efficiently. This is the primary inhibitor of two clotting factors that are required for the generation of thrombin. In people with congenital antithrombin deficiency, there is a reduced amount of this substance in the blood due to a genetic abnormality. Furthermore, other genetic disorders have been

This RUC encompasses the following patient profiles as identified in Step 1:

- inherited thrombophilia gene mutations,
- factor V Leiden,
- prothrombin Factor II,
- inflammatory bowel disease,
- ANCA-associated vasculitis,
- genetically predicted varicose veins,
- family history of DVT,
- non-O blood group.

⁷³ Miller, F. W. (2023). The increasing prevalence of autoimmunity and autoimmune diseases: An urgent call to action for improved understanding, diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. *Current Opinion in Immunology*, 80, 102266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coi.2022.102266>

⁷⁴ Conrad, N., Misra, S., Verbakel, J. Y., Verbeke, G., Molenberghs, G., Taylor, P. N., Mason, J., Sattar, N., McMurray, J. J. V., McInnes, I. B., Khunti, K., & Cambridge, G. (2023). Incidence, prevalence, and co-occurrence of autoimmune disorders over time and by age, sex, and socioeconomic status: A population-based cohort study of 22 million individuals in the UK. *Lancet (London, England)*, 401(10391), 1878-1890. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(23\)00457-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(23)00457-9)

⁷⁵ Cushman, M. (2005). Inherited Risk Factors for Venous Thrombosis. *Hematology*, 2005(1), 452-457. <https://doi.org/10.1182/asheducation-2005.1.452>

4.7.2. Risk factors and clinical background

Systemic inflammation modulates thrombotic responses by suppressing fibrinolysis, upregulating procoagulant, and downregulating anticoagulants, and autoimmune disorders such as systemic lupus erythematosus, inflammatory bowel disease, and Behçet's syndrome have been linked to an increased risk of VTE. Scientific comparative studies suggest that coagulation and innate immunity have a shared evolutionary origin, showing that the immune and coagulation systems are linked, with many molecular components being important for both systems⁷⁶.

Over some years now it has been shown that certain autoimmune disorders, such as systemic lupus erythematosus⁷⁷, inflammatory bowel disease and Behçet's syndrome^{78,79}, are linked to an increased risk of VTE. Nonetheless, the list of autoimmune and immune-mediated disorders linked to an increased risk of VTE has grown longer and longer, and now also includes rheumatoid arthritis⁸⁰, celiac disease⁸¹, hyperthyroidism⁸², and Wegener's granulomatosis⁸³.

In addition, two recent reports have linked a large number of autoimmune disorders/immune-mediated disease to an increased risk of VTE^{84,85}. Importantly, as we have seen in obesity, inflammation is a common feature of these disorders.

4.7.3. Patient's needs and ThrombUS+ added value

The main determinant for specificities in the co-creation of the design of the device would depend on the health status of the patient. In co-creation with the doctor and patient, the exact health status of the patient

⁷⁶ Zöller, B., Li, X., Sundquist, J., & Sundquist, K. (2012). Autoimmune diseases and venous thromboembolism: A review of the literature. *American Journal of Cardiovascular Disease*, 2(3), 171-183

⁷⁷ Peck, B., Hoffman, G. S., & Franck, W. A. (1978). Thrombophlebitis in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus. *JAMA*, 240(16), 1728-1730. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1978.03290160046020>

⁷⁸ Fabio, F. D., Lykoudis, P., & Gordon, P. H. (2011). Thromboembolism in Inflammatory Bowel Disease: An Insidious Association Requiring a High Degree of Vigilance. *Seminars in Thrombosis and Hemostasis*, 37, 220-225. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0031-1273086>

⁷⁹ Yazici, H., Fresko, I., & Yurdakul, S. (2007). Behçet's syndrome: Disease manifestations, management, and advances in treatment. *Nature Clinical Practice Rheumatology*, 3(3), 148-155. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncprheum0436>

⁸⁰ Matta, F., Singala, R., Yaekoub, A. Y., Najjar, R., & Stein, P. D. (2009). Risk of venous thromboembolism with rheumatoid arthritis. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 101(1), 134-138.

⁸¹ Ludvigsson, J. F., Welander, A., Lassila, R., Ekbom, A., & Montgomery, S. M. (2007). Risk of thromboembolism in 14,000 individuals with coeliac disease. *British Journal of Haematology*, 139(1), 121-127. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2141.2007.06766.x>

⁸² Lin, H.-C., Yang, L.-Y., & Kang, J.-H. (2010). Increased risk of pulmonary embolism among patients with hyperthyroidism: A 5-year follow-up study. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis: JTH*, 8(10), 2176-2181. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1538-7836.2010.03993.x>

⁸³ Merkel, P. A., Lo, G. H., Holbrook, J. T., Tibbs, A. K., Allen, N. B., Davis, J. C., Hoffman, G. S., McCune, W. J., St Clair, E. W., Specks, U., Spiera, R., Petri, M., Stone, J. H., & Wegener's Granulomatosis Etanercept Trial Research Group. (2005). Brief communication: High incidence of venous thrombotic events among patients with Wegener granulomatosis: the Wegener's Clinical Occurrence of Thrombosis (WeCLOT) Study. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 142(8), 620-626. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-142-8-200505030-00011>

⁸⁴ Ramagopalan, S. V., Wotton, C. J., Handel, A. E., Yeates, D., & Goldacre, M. J. (2011). Risk of venous thromboembolism in people admitted to hospital with selected immune-mediated diseases: Record-linkage study. *BMC Medicine*, 9, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1741-7015-9-1>

⁸⁵ Zöller, B., Li, X., Sundquist, J., & Sundquist, K. (2012). Autoimmune diseases and venous thromboembolism: A review of the literature. *American Journal of Cardiovascular Disease*, 2(3), 171-183.

should be established to ensure effective implementation of the device(s). Especially which autoimmune disease or genetic disorder the patient is suffering from is important to take into account.

In general, intermittent compression stockings with integrated ultrasound scanning for DVT could be an adequate design because it would both give mechanical prophylaxis that is needed for patients with autoimmune disease or genetic disorders, reduce the need for risky anticoagulant prophylaxis, and in the meantime, alert doctors if the situation gets critical and anticoagulant prophylaxis becomes fundamental.

4.7.4. High-level acceptability and design requirements

Considering patients with autoimmune disease or genetic disorder may experience rapid changes in their health situation, for example for multiple sclerosis patients when they have a new flare-up and lose control over body parts, the sensibility and flexibility of the device will be crucial to understand how long the device would be needed to be worn by the patient. Comfort and easiness of use of the device needs to be considered, since they already are fatigued from their medications (especially patients with autoimmune diseases) and have to adhere to multiple different treatments, and rely on several devices, so when adding a new one it must be easy to use and comfortable to ensure adherence.

Next, since autoimmune disease are chronic by character, patients might need to wear the device for months or years, and in some cases, depending on the characteristics and gravity of the disease, they would have to wear it for the rest of their life, alongside other devices and concurrent treatments.

4.8. Personas

4.8.1. Nikolas, 40 years old – Neurosurgery

Nikolas is 40 years old and a motorbike enthusiast. Every few weeks, he used to ride a few hundred kilometers with a group of friends. Last time, however, he had the very bad luck to be hit by a truck whose driver did not break in time. Nikolas was thrown off the motorbike and hit his head hard on the road. The helmet he was wearing saved his life but did not prevent him from suffering a traumatic brain injury, which required him to undergo emergency neurological surgery. Due to the known risk of bleeding and the increased risk of having to re-operate, the intervening medical team decided to keep anticoagulant prophylaxis to a minimum and to perform pneumatic compression manually. When Nikolas came out of surgery, he was admitted to the intensive care unit, where he had to remain immobile and in an induced coma for several days. In order to monitor the high risk of thrombosis that his condition entailed; nurses placed the ThrombUS+ device on Nikolas' legs. The device periodically screens and alerts them if it detects signs of deep vein thrombosis. The nurses thereby save time and resources while better monitoring for potential danger signs.

4.8.2. Laura, 65 years old – Lower limb orthopaedic surgery

Laura is 65 years old and loves playing with her young grandchildren. Last week she went out walking to buy a present for them, despite the bitter cold and the fact that the walkways were covered with ice. Unfortunately, Laura accidentally slipped and fell, hitting her hip against the cold ground. On arrival at the hospital, she was x-rayed and diagnosed with a hip fracture. In the preoperative study it was detected that Laura had family members who had suffered thrombosis events. Although she had no symptoms, the doctors considered it appropriate to perform an ultrasound before the operation, which was however negative. After the operation, which was successful, Laura was hospitalised and had to remain immobilised for ten days. Considering the risk of thrombosis due to the operation, her age and family history, but aware of the difficulty in moving and the pain caused for Laura to undergo ultrasound studies elsewhere, the doctors opted to place the ThrombUS+ device in her legs, which continuously monitors the potential formation of blood clots (in which case it triggers an alert) and does not require further intervention. Since full recovery will be lengthy and will require several months of reduced mobility and rehabilitation, the doctors suggested that Laura also use the device upon her discharge from the hospital.

4.8.3. Clément, 60 years old – Cardiovascular surgery and risk

Clément is a heavy smoker and suffers from diabetes. Although he doesn't move or exercise much, he began to experience sharp chest pain and shortness of breath, along with a strange sweating in his hands. Concerned, he went to see a cardiologist who performed a CT scan of his heart and detected a plaque in a coronary artery. He underwent coronary artery bypass graft (CABG) surgery 24 hours later, followed by 3 days of post-surgical observation. Although the pre-surgery DVT scan was negative, after the operation the doctors decided to place the ThrombUS+ device in Clément's legs to continuously monitor his blood flow in order to early detect a possible thrombosis. On the third day after the operation and hours before discharge, the ThrombUS+ issued an alert, indicating the possible generation of a thrombus in Clément's left leg. A cardiologist examined him manually and after diagnosing possible DVT prescribed a higher dose of anticoagulants, which Clément would have to continue taking for a few weeks.

4.8.4. Paula, 30 years old – Pregnant woman

Paula is in the sixth month of pregnancy of her second daughter. As in her first pregnancy, Paula has recurrent but mild headaches. After routine blood and urine tests, the obstetrician has diagnosed her with mild pre-eclampsia and has strongly advised her to keep moving as much as possible, given her increased risk of developing thrombosis due to her condition overall. Paula has already gone through one pregnancy and knows that because of her condition and the timing she is at an increased risk of VTE, which she must prevent. However, the compression stockings recommended by her obstetrician for her first pregnancy were too hot and uncomfortable, which resulted in her wearing them only rarely. This time, however, the obstetrician proposed that she could use the ThrombUS+ device, which Paula can wear on her own or with her partner's help and that is fresher and less invasive. The device allows to directly monitor for DVT indicators and sends alerts that can be accessed by her obstetrician if any abnormalities are detected.

4.8.5. Silvia, 60 years old – Cancer and oncological treatment

Silvia has been courageously battling cancer for an extended period. The cancer is located in her abdomen, leading to additional complications. At one point, she developed a condition causing her lymph nodes to swell and exert pressure on her inferior vena cava, the major vein that carries blood from her legs back to her heart, significantly increasing the risk of developing DVT. To prevent this, the doctors started Silvia on prophylactic treatment. Thankfully, the treatment was successful, and the lymph nodes reduced in size, alleviating the pressure on her vein. However, the concern remains that the lymph nodes might enlarge again without warning, posing a risk to her health, and once again increasing the risk of developing DVT. Silvia and her doctors now face an important decision: should she continue the burdensome prophylactic treatment indefinitely, or can it be safely discontinued? With the ThrombUS+ device, Silvia can safely stop taking the drugs, and only needs to wear the non-intrusive device at certain times during the day to monitor that blood clots are not forming. The device therefore allows her to interrupt the prophylactic treatment without fears and re-start it only once the device monitors the emergence of DVT and her doctors are alerted. The device provides early allowing for timely intervention, and finally offering Silvia peace of mind.

4.8.6. Olga, 35 years old – Obesity

Olga has lived with overweight for many years and after her last visit to medical specialists she has been diagnosed with obesity. The doctors have suggested her to work on improving her physical and dietary habits in order to cope with her physical pains and the sleep difficulties she experiences. But these habits are not easy to change, and the results take a long time. Her GP, however, has been particularly concerned when Olga mentioned that she was taking contraceptive pills regularly, because, he said, the combination of these and other risk factors derived from her medical condition could result in a very high risk of deep vein thrombosis, a life-threatening complication Olga had never heard of. To avoid unpleasant surprises, the doctor suggested Olga to use the ThrombUS+ device to periodically screen the areas of the body where blood clots are most likely to be generated. For this purpose, the wearable device is to be worn on the legs and

uses sensors to detect early signs of possible DVT. It is comfortable, easy to use and takes little time. If it detects signs of risk, it sends an alert to a mobile phone, which can then be shared with the clinician and facilitate taking preventive or correcting measures.

4.8.7. Alexander, 40 years old – Autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders

Alexander works in an office, where he spends most of his time sitting at the computer, and in his free time he plays music. Once a month he gets together with his university friends to play a football match. After the last one, Alexander noticed a pain in his calf, which he associated with physical exercise, so he did nothing about it. A few days later, he went to a scheduled appointment with his GP for a routine check-up, to whom he mentioned the persistent pain. Even though the patient looked healthy, the doctor, knowing that Alexander has a Factor V Leiden mutation that emerged from previous blood tests, suggested him to have a quick routine screening during the consultation with the ThrombUS+ wearable device. Alexander placed the device on his legs and waited some minutes while the doctor went to check on the next patient, until the device signalled completion and the doctor came back with the scan results. These alerted to the possible formation of a thrombus in the leg where he felt the pain, indicating the possibility that Alexander had an ongoing DVT. Thus, ThrombUS+ allowed early detection of possible indicators of a DVT event, and triggered the GP to consult a specialist to determine whether further testing and treatment was needed.

5. Conclusions

The objective of this Deliverable 2.1 has been to identify possible significant use cases for the ThrombUS+ device and to describe initial functional criteria that should be considered in the co-design process for each of such use cases. The exercise conducted within Task 2.1 “Patient-centric cases and requirements definition” and hereby presented here, aimed to contribute to the device’s co-design process by integrating medical needs, functional requirements and user acceptability constraints in a set of possible scenarios –which we named Reference Use Cases, RUCs—based on DVT-related patient conditions. Considering this is only the first step of the co-design process set under WP2, it was important to collect as much information as possible to allow for better design decisions in the coming stages. To this aim, we collected and processed extensive clinical information by assessing several patients’ profiles provided by the clinical partners of the consortium (ATHENA, CSS-IRCSS, GNP, HSV, LSMU and TAU) and by interviewing targeted experts to further deepen the understanding on current diagnostic and treatment practices. Moreover, we conducted a rapid literature review in order to both fill any remaining gaps and to bring the use cases in line with the scientific state of the art. In this way, knowledge of the functional circumstances in which the ThrombUS+ device could add the most value from a patient-centred approach was generated, thereby driving the device under development to remain both useful for clinical purposes and acceptable to patients and medical professionals.

The scenarios we established, the RUCs, intended to encompass respective sets of prevalent DVT patient profiles with similar main baseline clinical conditions or treatment features. Having RUCs as a measure of analysis and comparison consequently allows consideration of both the added value of the potential ThrombUS+ device for each patient’s journey and the (possibly) divergent technical and functional requirements to ensure the innovation’s usability, acceptability and cost-effectiveness in relation to each RUC. Based on the information collected, seven RUCs were constructed on generic clinical conditions or treatments – Neurosurgery, Lower limb orthopaedic surgery, Cardiovascular surgery and risk, Pregnancy and postpartum, Cancer and oncological treatment, Obesity, and Autoimmune diseases and genetic disorders. We especially focused on identifying for each RUC the potential added value of the ThrombUS+ device and the high-level functional requirements to ensure its usability, acceptability and cost-effectiveness.

While particular needs and potential avenues of usage were identified in each of the RUCs, there are some common and general points that are valuable to summarise. In terms of usability, i.e. the potential for the ThrombUS+ device to improve early detection of DVT and thus reduce its fatal consequences in an efficient

way, all clinical experts consulted agreed that the mere potential improvement in the sensitivity, specificity or confidence of the screening system would already be a significant step forward, given the relatively low level of confidence of current methods and the high incidence of asymptomatic cases. In terms of acceptability, there were unanimous views on the very high importance of ensuring user (patients and medical staff) engagement. To this end, it was stressed in all cases the importance of ensuring a fresh, comfortable and non-invasive (and of course not painful) wearable design, as well as a simple and effective interaction between the components and users. In terms of cost-effectiveness, it was logically highlighted that as long as the wearable device reduces clinical staff workload and the use of high-cost equipment, while increasing detection capacity, the impact would be expected to be positive. Remarkably, the use cases identified highlight a window of opportunity to create a device that could be used outside of the clinical setting. This is further supported by the fact that approximately 3 out of 4 DVT or PE events seem to occur outside the hospital^{86,87}. While remaining cautious about patient safety, the spectrum of outpatient uses is potentially relevant and worth considering⁸⁸.

Finally, there was also coincidence in all the consulted sources that the technical means that the tool may use must be carefully weighed against medical contraindications (e.g. the effects of performing electronic compression) and the limits set by the complexity of use and acceptability of the design. It is therefore relevant to discern at the next stages whether the device is to be designed with the aim of covering certain cases within the identified possible scenarios (and therefore adapted to their specific usability and acceptability needs) or whether a universally applicable design can be technically aimed for (a scenario that is likely to depend on technical possibilities).

Based on this Deliverable's outcomes and the work conducted within Task 2.1, the co-creation process to establish the needs and requirements will continue in the following Tasks 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 with the integration of specific regulatory, technical and functional requirements. ThrombUS+ will thus ensure a feasible design of the wearable device which appropriately addresses the clinical needs while remaining acceptable to the users.

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Annex 2 - Step 1 Literature References

Literature references provided by partners during the Step 1 of building the Reference-Use-Cases.

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Annex 3 – Step 2 Expert’s interview guide

1. Personal expertise

- 1.1. What is your professional background and what does your clinical specialization entail?
- 1.2. How often do you come across DVT cases where the main triggering condition seems to be [RUC]? Do you have a role in DVT screening, treating, and monitoring?

2. Clinical information

- 2.1. Given the [RUC] condition, what are the most relevant concurrent conditions [based on the concurrent factors list] that could increase the risk of DVT? Which ones are the most prevalent? Which ones increase DVT risk the most?
- 2.2. Are there significant differences in the risk of developing DVT for [RUC] based on age and/or gender?

3. Patient needs (Baseline condition)

- 3.1. Is the mobility of the patient somehow limited? Is the patient bedridden or relying on assisted mobility?
- 3.2. Is hospitalisation foreseen for [RUC]? How long? Is full recovery expected? After how long?
- 3.3. Is the patient able to address his/her own basic needs independently?
- 3.4. How often and when is the patient expected to interact with clinical facilities and/or staff?

4. Current DVT Screening, Treating, Monitoring Journey

- 4.1. Can you describe the standard DVT patient journey/protocol (considering screening, treating, and monitoring stages) specific to [RUC] patients? When and how are these three steps carried out? By whom? Are there relevant limitations or conditions to treat these patients?

5. Continuous DVT Monitoring

- 5.1. Would continuous monitoring for DVT improve detection and overall patients’ care for [RUC] cases? How?
- 5.2. Would continuous monitoring be a cost-effective solution? Will there be an added value (or savings) in terms of resource use, time management, accuracy, reliability, etc.?

6. Design

- 6.1. What would be, in your opinion, the optimal design for a continuous monitoring device tailored for [RUCs] patients? How would the average patient’s journey change?
- 6.2. Do you foresee significant issues with patients’ and clinicians’ acceptance of a device such as the one discussed? Do you foresee any other potential risks?

7. Conclusion

- 7.1. Is there anything we did not cover today you would like to add?

Thank you for your cooperation!